

**A SPEECH ACTS APPROACH TO THE ANALYSIS OF
SOME PUBLIC- SERVICE ADVERTISEMENTS
IN NIGERIA**

BY

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When we communicate some propositions to another person, we do so, normally, because we wish to influence in some ways his beliefs, his attitudes or his behaviour.

J.Lyons (1977:725)

ABSTRACT

The present study applies speech acts theory to the language of some public-service advertisements put out on radio in Nigeria to investigate the types of speech acts that characterize them, the relationships the speech acts contract with one another in a sequence, and the impact of cohesive elements on the speech acts.

In doing the above, the study provides an overview of the nature of public-service advertising and the contextual background of the public-service advertisements with which we are concerned. The public-service advertisements are limited to those concerned with Nigeria's drive for a new socio-economic and political order, with focus on the Structural Adjustment Programme, the Social Mobilization Programme, and the Political Education Programme.

In addition, the study outlines the theoretical framework used for the analysis and also provides some justification for

the choice of framework. Searle's version of the theory of speech acts is chosen as the framework for analyzing the data. The conceptual machinery of Searle's framework and its mechanics are outlined and a modification of part of his conceptual machinery is discussed. A framework for extending the application of speech acts theory in the present study is also provided.

In concluding the study, the writer draws attention to its major achievements and contributions and makes suggestions about possible directions for further research towards making speech acts theory more relevant to extended discourse in actual language usage.

The data on which the study is based is attached as an appendix.

DEDICATION

This thesis is affectionately and humbly dedicated

to

**THE LORD GOD ALMIGHTY
FATHER, SON, and HOLY SPIRIT**

The AUTHOR and FINISHER of this work

GREAT IS THY FAITHFULNESS, O LORD!

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CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by Miss Rosarri Chinedu Ude in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan.

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CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 AIMS:

The aim of the present study is to apply speech acts theory to the language of some public-service advertisements in Nigeria, to investigate both the types of speech acts that characterize them and the relationships which the speech acts contract with one another in a sequence.

In doing the above, attention will also be focused on the impact on the acts of whatever cohesive elements are in evidence in the public-service advertisements.

1.2 SCOPE:

The study centres around a speech acts analysis of some public-service advertisements concerned with Nigeria's drive for a new socio-economic and political order with special

focus on the Structural Adjustment Programme, the Social Mobilization Programme and the Political Education Programme.

The advertisements were recorded from Radio Nigeria, Lagos and Radio O-Y-O, Ibadan. The radio medium is chosen because many people have access to it, thus making it the most effective channel for the dissemination of information.

In other words, analyzing public-service advertisements collected from the radio is considered to be a more viable choice than dealing with data from any other mass medium because the advertisements in our corpus would probably have been heard by a larger target audience.

The public-service advertisements in the collection for this study are in Standard English and Nigerian Pidgin. The choice of public-service advertisements couched in Standard English and Nigerian Pidgin is conditioned by audience reach. Standard English and Nigerian Pidgin are spoken across the

country unlike the indigenous languages which are limited in geographical spread. The intention here is to study public-service advertisements which may have been heard by a wide variety of people from different ethnic groups in Nigeria.

1.3 SIGNIFICANCE:

The predominant type of research carried out on advertising is social or behavioural research, usually with the aim of improving marketing strategies. In effect, consumer advertising has received so much attention from researchers (cf. Donohue (1975); Goldberg and Gorn (1978); Rafeen (1988); Nwachukwu (1991); Ajala (1992); etc.) with very little attention paid to public-service advertising. Social or behavioural researchers have been interested in issues such as the role of persuasive communication in advertisements, advertising media and the strategies used by some manufacturing companies, the influence of a particular medium of advertising on audience brand loyalty, attitudes towards a particular medium's advertisement of some products/services, and so on.

However, there have been some research on the language of advertising, but these have usually been concerned with stylistic analysis of consumer advertisements. The only study on the application of speech acts theory to advertisements with which the present researcher is familiar is Adegbija's (1982) doctoral thesis which also focused on consumer advertisements.

It is the intention of the present researcher to focus on public-service advertisements with the aim of describing their nature via purely linguistic terms by applying speech acts theory to them. The focus on public-service advertisements is considered relevant because there is now an increasing use of these advertisements in Nigeria to enhance the mass mobilization process going on in the country. In other words, the messages evident in the advertisements are directed at influencing the beliefs, attitudes or behaviour of the generality of Nigerians in order to bring about some positive changes in the various spheres of life in the society. This would normally

imply that the messages contain speech acts such that the understanding of the messages that the public-service advertisements convey would depend on a prior understanding of such speech acts. It is to be hoped that one possible by-product of this study would be to point in the direction of the type of speech acts and speech act relationships evident in the advertisements that would be necessary to facilitate the understanding of the advertisements' message and perhaps bring about the intended reaction from the hearers.

It is hoped that the identification of the speech act types and the relationships evident in the public-service advertisements will throw some light on the linguistic characteristics of the advertisements and explicitly increase the linguistic awareness of copywriters in creating effective public-service advertisements.

In purely theoretical terms, the application of speech acts theory to public-service advertisements should properly contribute to extending the application of speech acts theory

beyond isolated and contrived sentences (to which it has tended to be applied) to extended discourse in actual language usage. By so doing, the interaction of speech acts within extended discourse will be portrayed. This research will, therefore, show the relevance of speech acts to real language use because our day-to-day interactions usually involve extended discourse rather than isolated sentences. It is also hoped that this study will throw some light on the effects of some textual features on speech acts.

1.4 Advertising: A Brief Overview

Advertising is a means through which ideas, goods or services are promoted with the intention of arousing a desire to buy or patronize them and/or invite action on, or agreement with the ideas conveyed (cf. Johnson (1978); Gilson and Berkman (1980); Dyer (1982); Douglas (1984); Doghudje (1987), etc.). In essence, therefore, advertising helps to sell ideas, goods or services through persuasion which is usually done by emphasizing desirable qualities.

Persuasion is an effective means of influencing the thinking, feeling and behaviour of people. It is a conscious attempt to influence the behaviour of the target audience. The message of the advertising text is, therefore, normally intended to persuade potential consumers to buy the advertised product or service. For instance, the Super Blue Omo detergent advertisement in one of the national magazines, goes thus:

SUPER Blue

OMO

Washes brighter ... and it shows. Super clean! Super bright! For that extra clean and bright wash all you need is Super Blue Omo. A handful of Super Blue Omo goes a long way! That is because Super Blue Omo has more concentrated power than any other blue detergent. Use Super Blue Omo for the whole family wash. It makes everything not just cleaner but also brighter. You can actually see the difference.

The desirable qualities in the above consumer advertisement are that Super Blue Omo detergent washes cleaner and brighter,

and the emphasis on the concentrated power of Super Blue Omo which guarantees cleaner and brighter wash is meant to persuade consumers to buy the product. Naturally, prospective consumers desire a cleaner and brighter wash.

Most advertisements aim at encouraging consumer action. In the competitive market, advertising serves as a marketing tool used to create preferences for advertised brands or services. Thus, Dyer (1982:13) says "advertisements are deliberate and consciously articulated messages". To be effective, the message of advertisements has to be so clearly and well presented as to ensure that the receiver makes little or no effort to understand what the message is about. The message may be verbal or visual or both. The verbal message is used to appeal to the audience's logical nature while the visual message is used to appeal to the emotions of the audience. The message plays an important role in persuasive communication.

The language, images, ideas, and values employed in the creation of advertisements are drawn from the culture of the

people. Thus, both the communicator and the receivers of the advertisements' message share common assumptions such that the copywriters take some things about communication for granted with the assumption that the audience would understand the message of the advertisements.

Advertisements are usually carried by paid mass media (print or electronic) on behalf of advertisers. Their presentation is usually non-personal. They are part of our everyday life in the sense that we see and hear many advertisements everyday. They are so pervasive: they assail the public on all fronts - in the newspapers and magazines, on television, over the radio, along the roads where they are displayed as outdoor advertisements, or distributed as handbills and posters, etc. In fact, they make up the greater proportion of the output of the mass media. Apart from informing, instructing and persuading, advertisements also entertain.

The foregoing exposition shows that advertising is a communication process which involves the four elements of

communication: source, message, channel, and receiver. The source of the message in the advertising communication system is where the message originates. The content of the advertising copy is the message. The channel is the medium through which the message is transmitted from source to the receiver. The target audience constitutes the receiver.

However, as Dyer (1982:4) notes, it is consumer advertising that “is perhaps the kind most visible in our society”. As earlier mentioned, consumer advertising has received so much attention from researchers with very little attention paid to public-service advertising (cf. 1.3). In order to bridge the wide gap between the amount of exposition on consumer advertising and that of public-service advertising, the present study focuses on public-service advertising.

1.5 PUBLIC-SERVICE ADVERTISING:

Public-service advertising is a kind of advertising outside the product/service realm. According to Gilson and Berkman

(1980:564), it is:

Communication presented in the conventional formats of advertising (i.e. typical newspaper or magazine space, radio or television time unit, in-town poster or country outdoor site, etc.) which urges its audience to implement or support some kind of social or economic cause deemed beneficial by the consensus of the broad general public ... Almost always, a public-service advertisement will specifically urge some kind of action.

Unlike consumer advertisements which contain what the consumers want to hear or do, public-service advertisements contain what the government or other authorities want the people to hear or do.

Public-service advertisements are used by the government or other authorities to convey particular/specific messages designed to achieve well-defined positive changes in the behaviour patterns of the different sectors and spheres of life in society [cf. Ude (1992)]. It is one of the most widely used

instruments of mass mobilization. An example of a public-service advertisement from our corpus (cf. Appendix A) is given below:

Text 8

One of the social ills in our midst is favouritism. Reward people on merit and not on other considerations.

This advertisement points out the right standard for rewarding people and implicitly condemns all other criteria.

Johnson (1978:258) enumerates the aims of the message of public-service advertising. They include:

- (i) Solution of social problems;
- (ii) Protection of the public;
- (iii) Promotion of civic activities;
- (iv) Raising money for clubs, institutions and charities;
- (v) Supporting the treatment of, or research on health problems.

These aims together show that the message of the advertisements are construed as being in the interest of the public. This much is in evidence in the illustrative public-service advertisement cited above.

Apart from the aims discussed in Johnson (1978:258) and outlined above, Johnson (ibid: p.261) further explains that “policy makers have become aware of the need to explain points of view and actions to an increasingly sceptical public”, thus accounting for the uses to which policy makers today put public-service advertising in a determined effort to persuade the public.

Public-service advertisements are different from public-service announcements. Public-service announcements serve a particular purpose within a short period of time, for example, asking some people to report for interview or duty at a particular place, date and time. Unlike public-service advertisements, public-service announcements do not affect people’s attitudes, beliefs or behaviour, rather they have to do with

an obligation that has to be fulfilled.

1.5.1 Motivation for Public-Service Advertising:

One of the motivating factors for public-service advertising is the need to remind and sensitize people to their rights and obligations as citizens. This essentially applies to the literate segments of society. In a society characterized by mass illiteracy, however, the motivating factor for public-service advertising will be the need to educate the masses on matters such as health, family planning, road safety, education, civic responsibilities including prompt payment of taxes, voting during elections, and so on.

There is no doubt that people's apathy and attitude of indifference to government may contribute to the necessity for public-service advertisements designed to correct identifiable negative attitudes. For instance, life in Nigeria today points to various negative attitudes which include nonchalant attitude to work, vandalization of public property, lack of patriotic spirit, bribery and corruption, embezzlement of public funds, elec-

toral malpractices, and so on, which will have to be corrected in order for the nation to make progress in all spheres of life. This probably explains why there are so many public-service advertisements aimed at promoting the appropriate positive attitudes among the generality of Nigerians.

The need for government to popularize its public programmes and persuade the people to comply with the tenets of the programmes may also be another motivating factor for widespread public-service advertising. For instance, there is in Nigeria today an increasing use of public-service advertising to popularize government programmes such as the Structural Adjustment Programme, Social Mobilization Programme, Political Education Programme, Family Planning Programme, Expanded Programme on Immunization, Environmental Sanitation Programme, Road Safety Programme, Campaign against smoking and drug-abuse, and so forth. Such public-service advertisements are used as part of a social engineering pro-

gramme aimed at mass mobilization.

1.6 Contextual Background of the Public-Service Advertisements:

This study will focus on the public-service advertisements that popularized the Structural Adjustment Programme, the Social Mobilization Programme and the Political Education Programme in Nigeria. The context of these public-service advertisements are highlighted below.

1.6.1 The Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP):

The process of economic growth and development in Nigeria, initially had agriculture as central focus. In the 1950's and 1960's, the greater percentage of government revenue accrued from the agricultural sector. In other words, Nigeria's exports were then mostly in the area of agricultural produce such as cocoa, cotton, groundnut, timber and rubber. The result was that the agricultural sector provided the majority of Nigerians with employment while catering adequately for domestic food supply such that food importation accounted for

only a negligible proportion of the total import bill. This is to say that agriculture played a very significant role in the Nigerian economy by its contributions to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment, government revenue, foreign exchange earnings and domestic food supply.

However, with the discovery of crude oil in commercial quantities, the focus of government shifted so much in the 1970's to the oil sector that the other sectors of the economy, such as agriculture and manufacturing, were relegated to the background. This caused structural defects in the Nigerian economy. The increase in petroleum oil prices and the increase in the volume of oil exports resulted in a substantial growth in government revenue coupled with expansion in expenditure. The money that accrued during this period of oil boom was invested in the provision of social, physical, and economic infrastructures, albeit inadequate. Unfortunately, the high dependence on the oil sector left the Nigerian government increasingly vulnerable to oil revenue fluctuations.

The effects of the 1981/82 drop in oil revenue were severe on the economy's balance of payment (BOP) and the economy, generally, so much so that Nigeria became a debtor-nation with its external debt increasing in a geometrical progression. To worsen the situation, imports increased, thus encouraging external dependence.

To stabilize the country's dwindling economy, the federal government adopted some administrative control measures. The major elements of the control measures, as mentioned by Ajewole (1988:10), include: (i) intensified rationing of foreign exchange through import licensing to reduce the demand for imports and aggregate demand in the economy, (ii) increase in tariffs, (iii) increase in interest rate by 2 percent across the board (iv) increase in gasoline prices, and (v) restrictions on capital transfers. However, although these control measures were gainful, the defective structure of the economy was not corrected; there was still a high level of imbalance in the economy's sectorial output and demand was still higher than supply.

In June, 1986, the federal military government, under President Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida, introduced the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP). The programme was a combination of both demand and supply-side management policies, such that, respectively, the level of aggregate demand in the economy would be reduced in the short run while the supply base of the economy would be improved over a longer period. Agriculture and manufacturing were categorized as “high priority sectors”. The main objectives of the Structural Adjustment Programme, as outlined by Ajewole (1988:11-12) were as follows:

- (i) to restructure and diversify the productive base of the economy in order to reduce dependence on the oil sector and on imports,
- (ii) to achieve balance of payments viability over the period,
- (iii) to lay the basis for a sustainable non-inflationary or minimal inflationary growth,
- (iv) to lessen the dominance of unproductive investments in the public sector, improve the sector’s efficiency and intensify the growth potential of the private sector.

To achieve the above objectives, the Structural Adjustment Programme provided for the following major policies:

- (i) the establishment of a foreign exchange market (FEM). The essence is to rely on market forces to determine the realistic exchange value of the Naira,
- (ii) trade and payments liberalization,
- (iii) tariff reform and rationalization to promote industrial diversification,
- (iv) deregulation/reduction of administrative controls and greater reliance on market forces,
- (v) adoption of appropriate pricing policies for petroleum products and public enterprise goods and services (i.e., removal of subsidies),
- (vi) rationalization and privatization of public enterprises,
- (vii) strengthening of existing demand management policies,
- (viii) adoption of measures to stimulate production and broaden the supply base of the economy. (Ajewole (1988:11-12))

The implementation of the Structural Adjustment Programme has brought such positive contributions to the management of the Nigerian economy as substitution of imported raw materials with local ones to encourage self-reliance. Other achievements of SAP as pointed out by Sam Aluko (1992) and reported in The Guardian of July 23, 1992, include: increase

in the production and export of agricultural cash crops, returns at fair prices for farmers on their products and abolition of marketing boards to enable farmers sell their export products when and where they desire; increase in the number of banking and other financial institutions since 1986 as a result of liberalization and deregulation of interest rates, thus making them more responsible to the demand and supply factors; and jettisoning of widespread subsidy of inefficient and unprofitable state-owned enterprises under the policy of privatization and commercialization.

Nevertheless, in spite of the above achievements of the Structural Adjustment programme, the gap between the hopes and the realities of the programme have continued to widen. The level of unemployment is still very high and the rate of inflation continues to gallop at such speed that it manifests in high cost of food items, enormous increase in house rent, school fees, hospital fees, transport fare, electricity bill, telephone bill, cost of fuel, and the like. The high cost of living generated by the repeated devaluation of the Naira has had an

adverse effect on the welfare and the standard of living of the populace. The resultant hardship has, at various times led to nationwide anti-SAP riots (as in May 1989 and May 1992). Similarly, the March, 1992, deregulation of foreign exchange transactions resulted in further depreciation of the Naira, leading to more disenchantment among the generality of the people.

In fact, in terms of social semiotics, the acronym "SAP" signifies different things to the people and to the government, respectively. To the people, SAP represents hunger, starvation, poverty, stringent hardship, deprivation of social services by removal of subsidies, followed by astronomical hikes in tariffs etc. In other words, SAP is understood in the sense of the verb "sap" because of the drain experienced from the programme. On the other hand, the government sees the acronym "SAP" in the sense of its meaning, i.e., Structural Adjustment Programme, which is to be understood as an economic recovery process which demands that the people should tighten their belts in order to achieve the objectives of the programme (mentioned earlier in this sub-section).

1.6.2 The Social Mobilization Programme:

The main task of the Social Mobilization Programme was to create national awareness and introduce positive changes in the attitude of Nigerians. It was also to create a new social order based on self-reliance. The programme was under the control of the Directorate for Social Mobilization.

The Social Mobilization Programme was launched on July 25, 1987, by President Ibrahim Babangida, after accepting part of the recommendations of the Political Bureau headed by S.J. Cookey. The Political Bureau recommended the adoption of a socialist ideology with all that it implies and the Social Mobilization Programme was recommended as part and parcel of what is required of an instrument for the kind of social engineering that the change envisaged. In other words, the Political Bureau recommended that in order to evolve a new political culture in Nigeria, the government should initiate a comprehensive, coherent and sustained programme of social mobilization and political education to educate and sensitize

the people to their rights and obligations to the country. However, government adopted the Social Mobilization Programme without taking the socialist ideology rather it decided to go “a little to the left and a little to the right”.

The Directorate for Social Mobilization was subsequently inaugurated on September 2, 1987, by the then Chief of General Staff, Vice Admiral Augustus Aikhomu, at Abuja. In order to empower the directorate, the federal military government enacted and promulgated Decree No. 31 of 1987, known as the Directorate for Social Mobilization Decree 1987. The directorate was charged with the task of implementing the objective of the social mobilization and political education programmes. The setting up of the directorate was part of the federal military government’s preparation to return the governance of the nation to a civilian administration. The directorate was to perform the following functions:

- (i) establish an appropriate framework for the positive mobilization and education of all Nigerians towards economic recovery and development, and a new social

- and political order;
- (ii) awaken the consciousness of all categories of Nigerians to their rights and obligations as citizens of Nigeria;
 - (iii) inculcate in all Nigerians the value and spirit of civic responsibility, commitment to social justice and economic self-reliance through mobilization and harnessing of their energies and natural resources into productive use;
 - (iv) sensitize, induct and equip all Nigerians to fight against internal and external domination of our resources by a few individuals and groups;
 - v) re-orientate all Nigerians to shun waste and vanity and to shed off all pretences of affluence in our life style;
 - (vi) promote pride in the consumption of home-produced commodities, and in self-reliance;
 - (vii) prepare the framework for creating the basic institutions and norms of democracy at all levels of our society;
 - (viii) create consciousness about power and its use, and about the proper role of Government in serving the collective interests of Nigerians;
 - (ix) ensure that materials which appear in the mass media, both electronic and the print, are in consonance with the national objectives of self-reliance, social justice, human rights, democratic norms, economic recovery and economic development;
 - (x) propagate the need to eschew all vices in public life, including corruption, dishonesty, electoral and census malpractices, ethnic and religious bigotry;

- (xi) propagate the virtues of hard-work, honesty, self-reliance, commitment to, and promotion of national integration;
- (xii) inculcate in all Nigerians the values of patriotism and positive participation in national affairs.

(MAMSER HANDBOOK, (1987:3))

From the perspectives of the Directorate, its first chairman, Jerry Gana, says:

Mobilization is the process of pooling together, harnessing, actualizing and utilizing potential human resources for the purpose of development. It is a process whereby human beings are made aware of the resources at their disposal, and are also motivated and energized to collectively utilize such resources for the improvement of their spiritual and material conditions of living. Mobilization of the creative energies of our people therefore lies at the root of genuine development.

["Our Mandate" in MAMSER
HANDBOOK (1987)]

Gana situates social mobilization in Nigeria within the framework of Nigeria's five national goals, that is, to build:

- (i) a united, strong and self-reliant nation;
- (ii) a great and dynamic economy;
- (iii) a just and egalitarian society;
- (iv) a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens;
- (v) a free and democratic society.

The three programmes of the Directorate for Social Mobilization were:

- (i) mass mobilization for self-reliance, social justice and economic recovery (MAMSER);
- (ii) political education;
- (iii) mass education.

1.6.3 The Political Education Programme:

This was one of the programmes of the Directorate for Social Mobilization. The aim of the Political Education Programme was to raise the political consciousness and maturity of the Nigerian masses in order to lay the foundation for a democratic political order in Nigeria in the third republic and beyond. The need for the political education programme arose from the fact that, as the Political Bureau reports:

.... a politically conscious, effectively mobilized and properly motivated population is the greatest deterrent to bad governance.

[cited in MAMSER HANDBOOK (1987)]

From the perspective of the Directorate, Gana points out that:

... political education in the Nigerian context can be described as a process of mental liberation which breaks down apathy and the culture of silence of the vast majority of Nigerians, and empowers them to participate effectively and meaningfully in the process of nation building.

[cited in Political Education Manual:

Towards a Free and Democratic Society (1989).]

In essence, the Social Mobilization Programme and the Political Education Programme were launched to inculcate appropriate social and political standards into Nigerians.

It is to be noted, however, that different kinds of mobilization programmes have been launched by previous regimes to create awareness and a sense of direction for Nigerians with

the intention of eradicating the social, economic and political ills in the society. These programmes include (i) Gowon's three R's of Reconciliation, Rehabilitation, and Reconstruction, which was launched after Nigeria's civil war in 1970 as an attempt to rebuild the nation after the civil war which lasted for about three years; (ii) the Low Profile Campaign of the Murtala/Obasanjo regime by which Nigerians were exhorted to shun ostentatious living and instead live and be seen to live within the means demonstrably available to them; (iii) the Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) of Obasanjo's regime which encouraged Nigerians to embrace farming to produce enough food for the nation; (iv) the Ethical and Green Revolutions of Alhaji Shehu Shagari's regime which were launched to effect a change in the orientation of Nigerians; and (v) the War Against Indiscipline (WAI) campaign of the Buhari/Idiagbon's regime which aimed at promoting and encouraging a "queuing up" culture or orderliness, work ethics, patriotism and nationalism, and an aversion for corruption and economic sabotage. These programmes, however, did not achieve the objectives for which they were established, thus explaining what may

have been perceived as the necessity to launch the Social Mobilization and Political Education Programmes of the Babangida regime.

It is against the backdrop provided by the preceding discussion of the social setting of the Structural Adjustment Programme, the Social Mobilization Programme, and the Political Education Programme, that the speech acts evident in the public-service advertisements in our corpus will be analyzed.

CHAPTER TWO

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 THEORETICAL ORIENTATION:

The choice of Speech Acts theory as the theoretical basis for the present study derives from the fact that as a theory that accounts for acts which language may be used to perform, speech acts theory provides a suitable means of achieving the basic aims of the present study.

Prior to the formulation of speech acts theory by J.L. Austin, truth conditions were viewed as central to meaning in language. The issue of the centrality of truth and falsity to meaning was the nucleus of the doctrine of logical positivism. The central tenet of this doctrine was that a sentence was only meaningful if it could be verified or tested for its truth or falsity. It was the pervasive doctrine in philosophical circles in the 1930's such that the formula for a theory of truth for formal language put forward in 1933 by Tarski (a logician), that is,
S is true if and only if P

(where S represents sentence and P refers to propositional content.)

was claimed to be significant to linguistics because it provided the basis of a theory of meaning for natural language. The claim is that to know the meaning of a sentence is to know under what conditions that sentence would be true. In other words, the meaning of a sentence is characterized by specifying the conditions that have to obtain in order for the sentence to be true.

Kempson (1977:27), however provides a modified version of the formula which is more restrictive than Tarki's 'S is true if and only if P' and it runs as follows:

S means that p $\equiv$ Necessarily S is true if and only if p

Kempson characterises the resultant modified version as being "equatable with a characterization of sentence meaning as the set of conditions minimally guaranteeing the truth of that sentence". Her formula captures the insight that "to give the

meaning of a sentence is to give the set of conditions which are both necessary and sufficient for the truth of that sentence” (ibid:p.27). For example:

- (a) “Akin caused Jide’s death” means that Jide died because Akin caused him to cease to be alive, if and only if, necessarily, “Akin caused Jide’s death” is true if and only if Jide died because Akin caused him to cease to be alive.

Kempson (1977:63) points out that

a theory of semantics based on truth provides a natural means of capturing the required predictions of an interpretation for each sentence of the language, of synonymy, ambiguity, entailment, etc.

However, this type of theory only accounts for one type of sentence: declarative, indicative sentences; it has no means of capturing what we mean by using interrogative or imperative sentences. In addition, it does not account for sentences in a declarative form which are not descriptions of events. Consider the following sentences:

- (b) I promise to buy you a bag.
- (c) I hereby apologize for banging the door.

These sentences are not descriptions of events, and as J.L. Austin (1962) first noticed, they cannot be said to be true or false, rather they could only be assessed as appropriate or not, and they could be characterized accordingly in terms of the differing sets of conditions necessary for their appropriate use. (These conditions are called either appropriacy conditions or felicity conditions.) Austin pointed out that these sentence types are used for performative purposes because they are not used for describing anything; uttering them is generally construed as performing particular kinds of actions. For example, the very utterance of sentence (b) above itself constitutes the performance of the action of promising and the utterance of sentence (c) is itself an action of apologizing. Austin's work on explicit performative utterances (ie., utterances whose illocutionary force is made explicit) led to the development of speech acts theory.

The basic tenet of speech acts theory is that we use

language to do things or to perform acts, and that there are many functions of, or ways in which we use speech. For instance, we use speech to advise, order, promise, request, assert, warn, criticize, apologize, and so on. Unlike truth conditional semantics which is intended as an account of sentence meaning (ie., abstract structured strings with semantic interpretation), Speech Acts theory is meant to give an account of acts of speech, of utterances (ie., individual tokens of sentences in context). A truth-conditional account of sentence meaning is part of a theory of linguistic competence while speech acts theory of utterance meaning is part of a theory of communicative competence or performance. Thus, the analysis of the data for this study (ie., public-service advertisements) is more amenable to speech acts theory because the advertisements contain utterances, ie, sentences in context.

Speech Acts theory provides insights into our use of language. The kind of insights thrown up by speech acts is part of what an adequate theory of pragmatics should account for.

Pragmatics is concerned with meaning in relation to a speech situation. Kempson (1975:138) describes linguistic pragmatics as “the study of sentences in use”, pointing out (Kempson 1977:68-69) that pragmatics aims at:

the explanation of how it is that speakers of any language can use the sentences of that language to convey messages which do not bear any necessary relation to the linguistic content of the sentences used. This type of theory would also have to explain the relation between the use of a sentence and the linguistic act (illocutionary act) which that sentence is used to perform.

Thus, pragmatics is an account of communication. The domain of pragmatics includes topics such as Cooperative Principles and Conversational Implicature, Politeness Principles, and Illocutionary Acts (ie, Speech Acts).

However, the whole gamut of pragmatics does not constitute the theoretical framework for this study. This is because, given the nature of public-service advertisements as discussed earlier (cf. 1.5 and 1.5.1), when the basic tenets of speech acts

theory are compared with those of the wider field of pragmatics outlined here above, there is little or no doubt that a speech acts outlook is better suited to cope with a meaningful analysis of such advertisements. In other words, since public-service advertisements are used by the government or other authorities to convey particular/specific messages designed to achieve well-defined positive changes in the behaviour patterns of the different sectors and sphere of life in society, they essentially carry direct messages which are necessarily related to the linguistic content of the sentence used. This means that the messages do not call for the hearers to make assumptions over and above the meaning of the sentences used by the speaker, rather they are concerned with telling the hearers exactly what to do. Thus, public-service advertisements look like material par excellence for testing out in the sense of validating or invalidating the predictions of speech acts theory and for confirming the viability of the theory or showing ways of enhancing this.

2.1.1 The Speech Acts Theory Adopted in the Present Study:

This study largely adopts Searle's theory of speech acts as outlined in his Speech Acts: An Essay in the Philosophy of Language where we are told that "the production or issuance of a sentence token under certain conditions is a speech act, and speech acts (...) are the basic or minimal units of linguistic communication" (ibid:p.16). The argument is that "a theory of language is part of a theory of action simply because speaking is a rule-governed form of behaviour" (ibid:p.17). Thus, speaking a language is performing speech acts such as making statements, giving commands, making promises, and so on, according to firmly established rules.

Like Austin, Searle distinguishes acts that are normally performed by someone who produces an utterance. He makes a distinction between an "illocutionary act" and a "perlocutionary act" such that an illocutionary act is the "complete" speech act whereas a perlocutionary act is the consequence or effect that an illocutionary act has on the actions, thoughts, beliefs, etc of the hearer(s). For example,

“by arguing I may persuade or convince someone; by warning him I may scare or alarm him; by making a request I may get him to do something; by informing him I may convince him (enlighten, edify, inspire him, get him to realize...)” (ibid:p.25).

The expressions underlined above denote perlocutionary acts. However, in place of the distinction which Austin makes between “locutionary” and “illocutionary” acts, Searle distinguishes “utterance acts”, that is, the act of uttering words, (which Austin calls “phatic acts”) from “propositional acts”, which refer and predicate and which largely match Austin’s “rhetic acts”. Thus, in the following example:

“Sam smokes habitually”. (ibid:p.22)

the speaker refers to or mentions or designates a certain object, Sam, and he predicates the expression “smokes habitually” of the object referred to. The illocutionary act performed in the above example is asserting. Thus, in performing an illocutionary act one characteristically performs utterance acts and propositional acts.

Searle points out that “the characteristic grammatical

form of the illocutionary act is the complete sentence (it can be a one-word sentence)” (ibid:p.25). Thus, sentence boundaries express speech act limits. However, the data for this study show that what the present writer calls 'message units' give a better delineation of speech acts than sentence boundaries. This is because each message unit contains a speech act while a sentence could contain more than one speech act where such sentence is a compound type. Message units are semantic rather than orthographic constructs. Each message unit expresses one complete identifiable point (cf. 2.3).

Searle rightly notes that the illocutionary acts are rule-governed in the sense that they are performed according to firmly established rules. On Searle's notion of rules, he distinguishes between regulative and constitutive rules. Regulative rules “regulate antecedently or independently existing forms of behaviour, for example, the rules of etiquette regulate interpersonal relationships, but these relationships exist independently of the rules of etiquette”. (ibid:p.33). In other words, regulative rules “regulate a pre-existing activity, an activity whose existence is logically independent of the rules”. They take the following form:

“Do X” or “If Y, do X” (ibid:p.34).

Thus, they characteristically take the form of imperatives, for

example, “when cutting food hold the knife in the right hand”. Constitutive rules, on the other hand, “do not merely regulate, they create or define new forms of behaviour; for example, the rules of football do not merely regulate the game of football but as it were create the possibility of or define that activity. The activity of playing football is constituted by acting in accordance with these rules; football has no existence apart from these rules. (ibid:p.33). This is to say that constitutive rules “constitute (and also regulate) an activity the existence of which is logically dependent on the rules” (ibid:p.34). Some constitutive rules, for example, take the following form: In a chess game, “a checkmate is made if the king is attacked in such a way that no move will leave it unattacked”. They are usually part of a system of activity, and thus take the following form:

“X counts as Y” or “X counts as Y in context C”.

(ibid:p.34)

In other words, constitutive rules “provide the basis for specifications of behaviour which could not be given in the absence

of the rule” (ibid:p.37). Searle argues that there are constitutive rules underlying speech acts such that the fact that the uttering of an illocutionary act such as promising (under appropriate conditions) counts as the undertaking of an obligation is a matter of rules. He enumerates the following semantic rules for the use of any function indicating device P for promising:

Rule 1: P is to be uttered only in the context of a sentence (or larger stretch of discourse) the utterance of which predicates some future act A of the speaker S.

Rule 2: P is to be uttered only if the hearer H would prefer S’s doing A to his not doing A.

Rule 3: P is to be uttered only if it is not obvious to both S and H that S will do A in the normal course of events.

Rule 4: P is to be uttered only if S intends to do A.

Rule 5: The utterance of P counts as the undertaking of an obligation to do A. (ibid:p.63)

Searle points out that these rules are ordered: rules 2-5 apply only if rule 1 is satisfied, and rule 5 applies only if rules 2 and

3 are satisfied as well. He notes that whereas rules 1-4 take the form of quasi-imperatives, i.e, they are of the form: utter P only if X, rule 5 is of the form: the utterance of P counts as Y. Thus rule 5 is of the kind peculiar to systems of constitutive rules.

Searle points out that the appropriacy or felicity conditions together define and constitute the nature of each speech act. He classifies these felicity conditions into propositional content conditions which specify restrictions on the content of the utterance; preparatory conditions that deal with the real-world prerequisites to each illocutionary act; sincerity conditions that specify the requisite beliefs, feelings and intentions of the speakers; and essential conditions that concern the particular purpose the speaker intends the utterance to count as. These felicity conditions exactly specify the appropriate context for the performance of an illocutionary act on an occasion of utterance. In other words, they are specifications for appropriate usage. For instance, for the issuance of an order to count as an order, the propositional content of the order must refer to a future act by the hearer while the three attendant

conditions are specified as follows:

The preparatory conditions include that the speaker should be in a position of authority over the hearer, the sincerity condition is that the speaker wants the ordered act done and the essential condition has to do with the fact that the speaker intends the utterance as an attempt to get the hearer to do the act. (ibid:p.64).

In this connection, consider the following public-service advertisement in our corpus:

TEXT 7

Be committed to your job.
A full day's pay demands
a full day's work.

The first speech act (ie., "Be committed to your job".) counts as ordering because its propositional content refers to a future act by the hearer, that is, becoming committed to his job. The preparatory condition of the speech act includes that

the speaker (ie, government) is in an appropriate position of authority, while its sincerity condition is that the speaker wants the hearer to, in his day to day approach to his job, provide evidence of a good measure of commitment to his job. Its essential condition has to do with the fact that the speaker intends the utterance as an attempt to get the hearer to behave in ways that indicate commitment to his job. The above conditions together describe the situation that must obtain for language users to construe what is heard as an order. This is to say that the performance of illocutionary acts within any language is based on specific rules.

Moreover, consider assertions, for example. The appropriacy or felicity conditions that exactly specify the appropriate usage of assertions are such that the propositional content condition of the assertion must commit the speaker to the truth of the expressed proposition while the three accompanying conditions are specified as follows:

The preparatory conditions include the fact that the hearer must have some basis for supposing the asserted proposition is

true, the sincerity condition is that he must believe it to be true, and the essential condition has to do with the fact that the utterance is an attempt to inform the hearer and convince him of its truth.

(ibid:p.64)

Thus, characteristically, each speech act has an underlying constitutive rule which makes it count as that particular speech act.

Searle's insistence on the need to capture both the intentional and conventional aspects of speech acts and the relationship between them leads him to revise the notion of meaning outlined in Grice (1957:377-388) by which:

To say that a speaker S meant something by X is to say that S intended the utterance of X to produce some effect in a hearer H by means of the recognition of this intention.

Searle's argument is that a notion of meaning based on intended effects not only fails to take into account the extent to which meaning can be a matter of rules or convention, but it also confuses illocutionary acts with perlocutionary acts. The point here is that saying something and meaning it are not a

simple matter of intending to perform a perlocutionary act but a matter of intending to perform an illocutionary act. He points out that there are many kinds of sentences used to perform illocutionary acts that have no perlocutionary effect associated with their meaning. For example, there is no associated perlocutionary effect of greeting in the sense that when a speaker says “Hello” and means it, he does not necessarily intend to produce or elicit any state or response action in his hearer other than the realisation that he is being greeted and wished well (Searle 1969:46). But that knowledge is simply understanding what is said, it is not an additional response or effect (ibid:p.46). Searle stresses that being understood rather than producing an effect on the hearer is the primary goal of an illocutionary act because the effect of an illocutionary act on the hearer is dependent on the hearer’s understanding of the speaker’s utterance. Searle’s standpoint strengthens Austin’s (1962) view that successful communication in performing an illocutionary act manifests as securing “uptake”, that is with the hearer recognizing the illocutionary act being performed. Similarly, Bach and Harnish (1979:3) argue that “in saying

something a person has a certain intention, and the act of communicating succeeds only if that intention is recognized by the hearer.” In other words, Austin, Searle, Bach and Harnish, all argue that the fulfilment of illocutionary intentions are a direct function of their being recognized.

2.1.2 Searle’s Classification of Speech Acts:

Searle’s classification of speech acts is based essentially on three major criteria: (1) “illocutionary point (or purpose)”, (2) “direction of fit between words and the world,” and (3) “expressed psychological state”. Other criteria presented in Searle (1976:1-7) include: “the force or strength with which the illocutionary point is presented”, “the status or position of the speaker and hearer as these bear on the illocutionary force of the utterance”, “the way the utterance relates to the interests of the speaker and hearer”, “the relations of the rest of the discourse”, “the propositional contents that are determined by illocutionary force-indicating devices”, etc.

The first essential criterion, illocutionary point”, is concerned with the “purpose” of the speech act. For instance, a

promise has the purpose of committing the speaker to do something, the point of an order is to get the hearer to do something; a description has the purpose of showing how (true or false, accurate or inaccurate, or whatever) something is. Searle notes that the illocutionary point is part of but not the same as illocutionary force and points out (ibid:p.3) that although the illocutionary point of a request is the same as that of a command in the sense that both are attempts to get hearers to do something, their illocutionary forces (i.e. various functions of speech such as ordering, requesting, etc) are clearly different.

The second major criterion, “direction of fit between words and the world”, deals with getting words to match the world or getting the world to match the words. For instance, assertions are instances in which we try to get our words to match the world (ibid:3). In this connection consider the second speech act in Text 7 above, (i.e., “A full day’s pay demands a full day’s work”.) This utterance is an assertion and its direction of fit is words to the world in the sense that the

words express what is generally assumed to be the case - it is generally the case that under normal circumstances, an employer expects an employee to give in exchange for whatever he is paid, work of commensurate or matching value. On the other hand, requests and orders are instances in which we try to get the world to match our words (ibid:p.3). Consider, in this connection, the first speech act in the same text 7 above, (i.e., "Be committed to your job."). This utterance is an order, and its direction of fit is world-to-word in the sense that the words express what the speaker expects the hearer to do, and which, when done, would cause the world at least, to look more like what the speaker meant his words to achieve - in the case under consideration, a new Nigerian society where people are committed to their jobs. Searle represents the word-to-world direction of fit with a downward arrow (↓) and the world-to-word direction of fit with an upward arrow (↑). He points out that the direction of fit is always a consequence of illocutionary point. For instance, the illocutionary point of "Be committed to your job" is to get the hearers to become more responsible by putting their best into their jobs, as a result, its direction of fit

aims at getting the world (i.e. the Nigerian society in this case) to achieve the illocutionary point or purpose.

Searle's third essential criterion "the expressed psychological state", deals with the sincerity conditions of the illocutionary act. Thus, "a man who states, explains, asserts or claims that p expresses the belief that p; a man who promises, vows, threatens, or pledges to do a expresses an intention to do a; a man who orders, commands, requests H to do A expresses a desire (want, wish) that H do A; a man who apologizes for doing A expresses regret at having done A; etc (ibid:p.4). This is to say that "in the performance of any illocutionary act with a propositional content, the speaker expresses some attitude, state, etc to that propositional content" (ibid:p.4).

Searle classifies illocutionary acts into five categories: Representatives, Directives, Commissive, Expressives, and Declarations. Searle notes that the point or purpose of Representatives is "to commit the speaker (in varying degrees) to something's being the case, to the truth of the expressed proposition" (ibid:p.10). They can be assessed as either true or

false. Their direction of fit is 'words to the world' and the psychological state expressed is 'Belief (that p)'. Representatives are symbolized as follows:

(Where (i) represents an assertion sign,
 (ii) the words-to-world direction of fit,
 (iii) B the sincerity condition of belief, and
 (iv) P the propositional content.) (ibid:p.10)

Some verbs that denote representatives are boast, describe, conclude, predict, deduce, etc. This class contains most of Austin's Expositives and many of his Verdictives.

In analyzing the speech acts contained in the public-service advertisements with which we are concerned, the term Assertive, instead of the term Representative, will be used because Searle in his (1979) version of classification of illocutionary acts refers to the class of Representatives as Assertives, thus, we would prefer to use the more current term which in any case seems to us to be more descriptively adequate.

The second category of illocutionary acts is Directives. Its illocutionary point is “to get the hearer to do something” (ibid:p.11). The direction of fit is world-to-words; this is to say that the speaker tries to get reality to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state is want (or wish or desire). The propositional content is always that the Hearer (H) does some future action A (ibid:p.11). Directives are symbolized as follows:

!↑W(H does A)

(Where the exclamation mark represents the illocutionary point-indicating device for members of this class, the upward arrow represents the world-to-word direction of fit, and W represents the sincerity condition.)

Examples of verbs denoting members of this class are: ask, order, command, request, beg, pray, entreat, invite, advise, etc. Some of Austin’s Behabitives such as dare, defy, and challenge, and many of his Exercitives belong to Searle’s class of Directives.

Searle in his third category of speech acts, **Commissives**,

retains Austin's definition of Commissives, while excluding verbs such as shall, intend, favour, etc, from this category. For Searle, Commissives are "those illocutionary acts whose point is to commit the speaker, (again in varying degrees) to some future course of action". (ibid:p.11). Examples of verbs denoting members of this class include: promise, vow, and pledge. Like the Directives, the direction of fit for Commissives is world-to-words. However, the difference between Commissives and Directives has to do with where commitment lies, as between speaker and hearer. In the case of Commissives, commitment to some future action lies with the speaker while in the case of Directives, it is the hearer that is expected to do some future action. The propositional content of Commissives is always that the speaker S does some future action A. The sincerity condition is intention, that is, the speaker must intend to do the future action A. Representing the members of this class with C, generally we have the following symbolism:

C↑I (S does A)

(Where I (i.e., first person singular pronoun) and S (i.e.,

speaker) refer to the same entity.)

The fourth category of speech acts is Expressives. Its illocutionary point is “to express the psychological state specified in the sincerity condition about a state of affairs specified in the propositional content” (ibid: p. 12) Verbs denoting Expressives include thank, congratulate, apologize, condole, deplore, and welcome. There is no direction of fit in Expressives because the speaker is “neither trying to get the world to match the words nor the words to match the world, rather the truth of the expressed proposition is presupposed” (ibid: p. 12) Thus, for example, when I apologize for having stepped on someone’s toe, my purpose is not to merely claim that a particular toe was stepped on, rather the fact that a given toe was stepped on is presupposed, and I regret stepping on the toe in question. Searle points out that in the syntax (of English), the expressive verbs will not take that clauses in their performative occurrence instead, they require a gerundive nominalization transformation. Thus, one cannot say:

*I apologize that I stepped on your toe.
rather the appropriate English form would be:

I apologize for stepping on your toe.

Similarly, one cannot have

*I congratulate you that you won the race.

nor

*I thank you that you paid me the money.

One would have:

I congratulate you on winning the race.

(Congratulations on winning the race)

I thank you for paying me the money.

(Thanks for paying me the money)

(ibid: p. 12)

Searle suggests that these syntactic facts are consequences of the fact that there is no direction of fit in Expressives. In an expressive, the truth of the proposition expressed is presupposed. Expressives are symbolized as follows:

$$E \phi (P) (S/H + \text{property})$$

(Where .E indicates the illocutionary point common to all expressives, ϕ is the null symbol indicating no direction of fit, P is a variable ranging over the different possible psychological states expressed in the performance of the illocutionary acts in

this class, and the propositional content ascribes some property (not necessarily in action) to either S or H. I can congratulate you not only on your winning the race, but also on your good looks. The property specified in the propositional content of an expressive must, however, be related to S or H.) (ibid: p. 12)

Searle's fifth and final category of speech acts is Declarations. In this class, "the state of affairs represented in the proposition expressed is realized or brought into existence by the illocutionary force-indicating device" (ibid: p. 13) This is to say that "saying makes it so," thus echoing Austin. Searle points out that the defining characteristic of Declarations is that the successful performance of one of its members brings about correspondence between the propositional content and reality, that is, successful performance guarantees that the propositional content corresponds to the world such that if I successfully perform the act of appointing you chairman, then you are chairman; if I successfully perform the act of declaring a state of war, then war is on; if I successfully perform the act of

marrying you, then you are married to me (ibid: p. 13) In order that the declaration be successfully performed, extra-linguistic institutions and a system of constitutive rules of language are involved. It is only when the declarations concern language itself such as when one says, I define, I call, etc. that extra-linguistic institutions are not required (ibid: pp 14 - 15). The structure of Declarations is symbolized as follows:

$$D \updownarrow \phi (P)$$

(Where D indicates the declarational illocutionary point; the direction of fit is both words-to-world and world-to-words because of the peculiar character of declarations; there is no sincerity condition, hence we have the null symbol in the sincerity condition slot; and we use the usual propositional variable p.) (ibid: p. 15)

Searle points out that some members of the class of declarations overlap with members of the class of representatives. This is because, as he notes, "some institutions require representative claims to be issued with the force of declarations in order that the argument over the truth of the claims can

come to an end somewhere and the next institutional steps which wait on the settling of the factual issue can proceed ..” (ibid: p. 15) Searle calls this class “Representative declarations”. Unlike the other declarations, they share with representatives a sincerity condition. Examples of such representative declarations are “I nominate you”, “I fire you”. This class is symbolized as follows:

$$Dr \downarrow \updownarrow B(p)$$

(Where Dr indicates the illocutionary point of issuing a representative with the force of a declaration, the first arrow indicates the representative direction of fit, the second indicates the declarational direction of fit, the sincerity condition is belief and the p represents the propositional content.) (ibid:p.16).

2.1.3 Strengths and Weaknesses of Searle’s

Classification:

Searle’s classification of speech acts, unlike Austin’s, is based on some clear criteria for distinguishing one kind of illocutionary act from another, thus, making his classification

more systematic. The three most important bases of his classification are illocutionary point, direction of fit, and expressed psychological state. Searle's criteria make it easy to assign illocutionary acts to specific categories. Moreover, they help to remove the kind of avoidable overlaps contained in Austin's classification.

Following Adegbija (1982: 66 - 67), the present writer notes that the duplication of fit in Directives and Commissives, however, constitutes a weakness for Searle's classification. Both categories of illocutionary acts have a world-to-word direction of fit, hence, we have two classes with the same direction of fit. However, the other two major criteria: illocutionary point and expressed psychological state (i.e., sincerity condition) help us to avoid the confusion that such duplication could easily have engendered.

Searle's classification of speech acts has been criticized on other grounds. Hancher (1979) points out that Searle's classification did not take into account "two kinds of

illocutionary acts: (1) illocutionary acts that combine commissive with directive illocutionary force (e.g., offering, inviting, challenging), and (2) illocutionary acts that require two participants (e.g., giving, selling, contracting). In defence of the first kind of illocutionary act, Hancher (1979:6) says:

Consider inviting, which is similar to offering. Searle (1976:11) classifies inviting as a directive; and 'when I invite you to do something', I am indeed trying to direct your behaviour. But more than that is involved. If I invite you to my party and then refuse to let you in, you will normally have grounds to object. The reason for this is that an invitation is not only a directive but a commissive: it commits the speaker to a certain course of behaviour himself.

Offering has the same double nature. To offer something to someone is both to try to direct that person's behaviour, and also to commit oneself to a corresponding course of behaviour. In offering you wine I am trying to get you to drink wine and also committing myself to

provide you with wine to drink.

Offering, tendering, bidding, inviting, volunteering, and formal challenging are all hybrid speech acts that combine directive with commissive illocutionary force. As such they need to be specially provided for in Searle's taxonomy. Let us call them commissive directives.

Hancher notes that unlike Searle's representative declarations where the declarative force overrides its representative force which makes it a subclass of declarations, "commissive directives are equally commissive and directive; neither force dominates. The class is sui generis" (ibid: p. 6). He calls commissive directives "pre-cooperative" illocutionary acts. The second kind of illocutionary acts, that is, illocutionary acts that require two participants (e.g., giving, selling, contracting), is the type he calls cooperative illocutionary acts - cooperative declarations, as in the case of giving, or cooperative commissives, as in the case of bilateral contracts (ibid: p. 15) Explicating this second kind of illocutionary act, Hancher says:

Therefore, one kind of illocutionary act,

the declaration giving (or gift), is compounded of two other illocutionary acts involving two speakers: a commissive directive offer matched by a declarative acceptance. Giving is a cooperative illocutionary act. (ibid: p. 7).

And the case is similar if we exchange promises. If I offer to promise to deliver my canoe to you next August on condition that you promise to deliver \$100 to me in return, and if you accept my offer by so promising, then our exchange of promises constitutes what is technically called a bilateral contract (the most ordinary kind of contract). Clearly, bilateral contracts, too, are cooperative illocutionary acts. (ibid: p. 8).

Hancher suggests that these two kinds of illocutionary acts:

(1) Commissive directives and (2) cooperative illocutionary acts, should be incorporated into Searle's classification of illocutionary acts to make it more comprehensive. He also points out that Searle is wrong to classify marrying as a declaration because marrying is a bilateral contract undertaken

in special circumstances and in the presence of special witnesses, thus, he classifies it as cooperative commissive. We agree with Hancher that there is need for the class of commissive directives and that Searle is wrong to classify marrying as a declaration. Incorporating these modifications into Searle's classification will significantly enhance the viability of his classification and therefore improve its capacity to give a comprehensive and accurate delineation of the different kinds of speech acts that exist. In this connection, we, therefore, attempt to incorporate the commissive-directive into Searle's classification of speech acts by classifying it as a compound speech act that combines all the features of both the commissive class and that of the directive class on equal grounds (cf. 2. 1. 2.). Neither the commissive nor the directive dominates. The commissive-directive class will be symbolized as follows:

$$C \uparrow I (S \text{ does } A) + ! \uparrow W (H \text{ does } A)$$

(Where C represents the illocutionary point - indicating device for members of the commissive class, the upward arrow represents the world-to-words direction of fit, I (i.e, first

person singular pronoun) and S (i.e, speaker) refer to the same entity, + represents compounding, ! represents the illocutionary point - indicating device for members of the directive class, the upward arrow represents the world-to-words direction of fit, and W represents the sincerity condition of want (that the hearer (H) does A.)

2.1.4. Justification of the Choice of Searle's Theory of Speech Acts:

The choice of speech acts theory as framework for this study has already been shown to derive directly from what we know of the nature of public-service advertisements and/or the assumptions that usually give birth to them as well as the goals/objectives normally associated with their use across the world. However, there are various versions of speech acts theory such as Austin's (1962) convention-based theory, Searle's (1969) theory of speech acts, Sadock's (1974) "abstract-performative hypothesis", Bach and Harnish's (1979) intention and inference-based theory of speech acts, and Adegbija's (1982) "pragmasociolinguistic" theory of speech acts. Among these

competing versions of speech acts theory, Searle's version is chosen as the model for this study.

The choice of Searle's variant of speech acts theory over and above other competing versions centres around its clarity in not just what exactly constitutes a speech act but where each such act belongs in the system such that the analyst is left in little or no doubt as to what to do with the material before him/her.

In addition, Searle's theory of speech acts, unlike the other speech acts theories, provides constitutive rules as the basic rules that underlie speech acts. The constitutive rules provide insights into the underlying nature of speech acts in terms that explicate the basis on which Searle argues that "speaking a language is engaging in a rule-governed form of behaviour." The point here is that the constitutive rules, which underlie speech acts, specify the necessary and sufficient conditions for the performance of particular kinds of speech acts; to this extent, speaking a language does boil down to performing particular acts according to firmly established

rules. The implication of constitutive rules for language is that they basically determine the nature, place and role of particular types of speech acts, such as promising, asserting, ordering, and so on. Thus, constitutive rules are significant to the explication of the underlying nature of speech acts. They provide the basis for distinctly specifying different types of speech acts, thus accounting for the classification of different types of speech acts.

Searle's classification of speech acts, unlike Austin's, is based on some clear criteria for distinguishing one kind of illocutionary act from another, thus, making it more systematic. The criteria themselves also make it easy to assign illocutionary acts to particular categories, thus creating a firm and vital link between the classification and Searle's theory of speech acts. As earlier mentioned, the three most important bases of his classification are illocutionary point, direction of fit, and expressed psychological state.

Though Bach and Harnish (1979) give a comprehensive

delineation of the varieties of speech acts possible in each of the major categories they recognize, some of the sub-classes they establish are not sufficiently distinguished, one from the other. For instance, the definitions they provide for Assertives and Informatives, Ascriptives and Descriptives, Concessives and Assentives, and so on, [cf. Bach and Harnish (1979:42-44)] do not show evidence of being able to set these sub-classes as distinctively apart as the analyst would have been led to expect. For example, they define Assertives as speech acts that "are characterized by S's expression of belief in a proposition (that P), and the intention that the hearer (H) also believe that P"; and the Informatives are said to be "speech acts in which S expresses the belief that P and also the intention that H form the belief that P." The point here is that the distinctions they attempt to establish somehow end up being fuzzy, thus failing to yield significantly distinguished classes.

Inasmuch as Adegbija's "pragmasociolinguistic" theory incorporates the recognition of the pragmatics of the situation which include the cognitive and the affective states of the

participants, special relationships obtaining among participants, mutual belief, understandings, or lack of these, and the nature of the discourse and how this relates to the interests of both the hearer and the speaker and to the context of interaction; nevertheless, his theory tilts largely towards Bach and Harnish's theory which he himself criticized. Adegbija criticizes Bach and Harnish's theory of speech acts for placing too much of emphasis on the recognition of intention and therefore neglect the role of conventional roles implicit in the recognition of some illocutionary forces. He also points out that some of Bach and Harnish's subclasses of speech as seem to have no clear criteria that distinguish them. For instance, he notes that definitions of Assertives and Informatives, and Ascriptives and Descriptives, etc, are almost the same and can be easily confused. Consequently, his (ie Adegbija's) analysis faces the problem of being fuzzy because some of the speech acts types he identifies overlap with one another. In this connection, consider the following sample analysis from his work:

Sample Analysis

- B. Vegfru Tomato Juice ad (Ap. p. 22)**
- (1) New - Informative**
 - (2) Vegfru Tomato Juice - Informative**
 - (3) 35k - Informative**
 - (4) Naturally Refreshing ... Anytime Anywhere ...
- Assertive**
 - (5) Easy to open - Assertive**
 - (6) Just flip the lid with the finger - Requestive**
 - (7) No need of any opener - Dissentive**
 - (8) Extracted from farm fresh tomatoes - Informative**
 - (9) Packed under strict hygienic conditions ... untouched
by hand - Informative**
 - (10) Full of all the nutrition tomato can give - Assertive**
 - (11) Drink Vegfru Tomato Juice daily for health and
vigour - Advisory**
 - (12) Available in all leading stores and supermarkets -
Informative**

In the above sample analysis, the assertives overlap with the

informatives such that they can be confused with one another. For instance, speech act numbers 4, 5 and 10 which Adegbija classifies as assertives could fit into the class of informatives as well, and vice versa. This overlap results from Bach and Harnish's inability to set some of the sub-classes distinctively apart which is the major deficiency of their classification, and which in turn weakens Adegbija's analysis. Interestingly, Adegbija himself points out this problem as part of the limitations of Bach and Harnish's theory of speech acts. It is against this background that we find ourselves compelled, as it were, to adopt Searle's decidedly more systematic classification.

2.2 LITERATURE REVIEW:

As earlier mentioned (cf. 1. 3), the only study on the application of speech acts theory to advertisements with which the present writer is familiar is Adegbija's (1982) doctoral thesis which focused on consumer advertisements. Adegbija's thesis titled A Speech Act Analysis of Consumer Advertise-

ments sets out to apply Speech Acts theory to the language of advertising with the intention of filling two gaps - the one left by Leech (1966) and the other left by speech acts theorists. He notes that Leech's (1966) study of advertising is a detailed and excellent study of the form of language, rather than its meaning or transmission. Adegbija points out that no major semantic study has been done on the language of advertising, and that this fact creates a gap in the study of the language of advertising. It is this gap that he sets out to fill by applying speech acts theory to the language of advertising. In addition, he set out "to probe into how advertising language relates to its purpose in spite of the apparent indirectness or unrelatedness of most of the speech acts used in advertising language to the real purpose of consumer advertising - that of merchandizing products and services". In other words, he deals with factors that are involved in encoding and decoding advertisements, which are the essential aspects of the transmission of advertisements.

Adegbija's study is innovative in the sense that it not only analyzes extended discourse, but also concentrates on actual

use of language in a social institution, consumer advertising, rather than on contrived utterances. He provides a theory of speech acts which is a synthesis of the theories of speech acts presented by Austin (1962), Searle (1969, 1979), Sadock (1974), and Bach and Harnish (1979). In other words, he attempts what he describes as "a unified and balanced theory of speech acts."

Adegbija argues that Austin and Searle place too much emphasis on convention as the determining factor in identifying and interpreting the illocutionary force of an utterance. He, however, points out that Searle suggests the involvement of 'intention' in the process of recognizing and interpreting illocutionary force; but his theory is evidently biased in favour of conventional or constitutive rules as the primary determinant of illocutionary force. He argues that both Austin and Searle seem to relegate the pragmatics of a situation of social interaction to the background. In addition, Adegbija notes that Sadock took full cognizance of linguistic convention, but neglected other crucial aspects of a situation of verbal interac-

tion such as intention and the pragmatics of a situation of social interaction. Bach and Harnish, on their part, place too much emphasis on the recognition of intention and therefore neglect the role of conventional rules implicit in the recognition of some illocutionary forces. Although they grant conventional status to a few speech acts, they deny such speech acts the status of being communicative. Adegbija, therefore, concludes that none of those earlier theories is balanced because each either tends to over-emphasize one variable or completely neglects pertinent factors usually involved in the performance and interpretation of speech acts; as a result, they do not, according to him, take full cognizance of the fact that the performance of speech acts is a multi-faceted type of human activity.

Adegbija, however, agrees with Bach and Harnish that understanding speech acts is, in the main, an inferential process. Following Austin and Searle, he assumes that we characteristically perform acts with our utterances. Such acts may be indicated by performative formulae but need not always be. He

also distinguishes illocutionary acts and perlocutionary effects such that perlocutionary effects refer to the effects achieved by our acts of saying something whether intended or unintended. He notes that while illocutionary acts may be conventional, as Austin and Searle clearly argue, they need not always be. This is because, as he points out, the force of some illocutionary acts is determined by the intention of the speaker. Others still may have to do with the pragmatics of the particular situation of social interaction. Thus, an inferential process is nurtured by the pragmatics of the situation, the social relationship obtaining between the participants, and the linguistic elements used in performing the illocutionary act. Adegbija calls all these factors the "pragmasociolinguistic context". Such a context need not have anything to do with the recognition of any fixed or specific intention on the part of the speaker.

He points out that the pragmatics of a situation of social interaction may include any, or all of the following factors:

- (a) The cognitive or affective states of the participants.

- (b) Special relationships obtaining among participants.
- (c) Mutual beliefs, understandings, or lack of these.
- (d) The nature of the discourse and how this relates to the interests of both the hearer and the speaker and to the context of interaction.

Adegbija insists that performing a speech act in any language is a total human activity in which language not only interacts with, and capitalizes on, but also relies simultaneously on pragmaticsociolinguistic factors for full import.

He examines 100 automobile, food, and medicine advertisements randomly selected from the Nigerian Daily Times of the first six months of 1981. The samples were taken at three-day intervals such that two days are omitted between samples. 44 automobile advertisements, 29 food advertisements and 27 advertisements on medicinal items were randomly sampled for the study. The advertisements were subjected to detailed analysis with a view to showing what types of speech acts are present in them, what propositional attitudes they express, what rhetorical strategies they employ, which verbal means contribute to the related propositional attitudes, which ones

comment on the speech act itself, and what pragmatic backgrounds they assume. He also investigates the kinds of implicature evident in the advertisements, and how, according to the evidence, they achieve their purpose.

In dealing with the encoding of the speech acts in the consumer advertisements, Adegbija handles issues such as master speech acts, motivation for master speech acts, the function of constative speech acts in consumer advertisements, evaluative constatives, speech act sequencing in advertisements and potential for ambiguity in speech acts in advertisements. However, in dealing with speech acts sequencing in consumer advertisements, Adegbija focuses on just how the speech acts are sequenced in general and how the sequencing brings about a nesting structure. He shows how the types of speech acts contained in the advertisements are ordered sequentially or linearly, and points out that there are some basic ways in which a unified structure is imposed on advertisements. These are:

(1) The introduction of a "topic", that is, usually the advertised

product. This topic is often repeated again and again and several "comments" are made on it.

- (2) Dependence on the reader's competence in being able to link one speech act with another, especially when some elements of a linguistic string are missing; and dependence on the reader's ability to create or imagine appropriate contexts for each advertisement. For example, when the **Fevemed ad** {Adegbija (1982: Ap. p. 18) } begins:

Fevemed

The two way action medicine.

the reader is trusted to be able to supply the missing copula on his own and therefore be able to realize that there is a connection between "Fevemed" and "the two way action medicine".

- (3) More important for achieving unity among the speech acts used in advertisements, however, is the nesting pattern by which one proposition is linked with another. Three such patterns which play a very important role in advertising may be identified:

- (a) Underlying nesting
- (b) Structural nesting
- (c) Intra-speech act nesting.

The basic underlying structure of advertisements is summarized thus: "the linking of A (the condition or problem necessitating use) with B (the product or service advertised), and C (the qualities or benefits to be derived)". For example, if you have skin health problem, use Dettol, and you will have full authority over your health. The structural nesting, on the other hand, depends crucially on conventional logic and argumentation. Adegbija notes that conventional logic is often used to provide a unified structure that links the speech acts: e.g., X is good, X will do Y for you. Therefore, buy X. The Premier ad, for example, says Premier is the beer that promotes a real feeling of friendship in homes, in parties, etc, therefore, "Make it Premier", "Beer for you and your friends". He points out that the reader is expected to be able to recognize such logic, just as he is expected to be able to recognize the illocutionary force of each advertisement. The intra-speech act nesting, for its

part, refers to the frequent pattern in advertisements in which two or more propositions may be nested in a major one. Adegbija points out that this is achieved primarily by means of linguistic devices, the most important of which are embedding and conjunction. He exemplifies this nesting pattern with the Sorbiline ad which begins:

SORBILINE

**Important to mothers, essential to
children, trusted for generations.**

He notes that one way of analyzing the above sample is to say that it contains three informatives. However, he adopts an alternative approach to the sample which is that three micro-propositions are nested in one major informative:

- (1) [Sorbiline is] important to mothers
- (2) [Sorbiline is] essential to children
- (3) [Sorbiline has been] trusted for
generations.

He points out that the nesting is achieved by means of an elliptical conjunction as shown in the Sorbiline advertisement text above.

However, in discussing speech act sequencing, Adegbija pays little or no attention to the types of relationships, if any, that exists between the speech acts in a sequence within a discourse.

The data for the present study reveals that different types of relationships do exist between speech acts sequences, and it points to the necessity for further extension of the application of speech acts theory to extended discourse. Thus, the present study, as a way of contributing to extending the application of speech acts theory to extended discourse, intends to show that speech acts in a sequence within a discourse contract some kind of relationship with one another. In addition, the present work goes further to show that cohesive elements play some role in bringing out the fact that speech acts within a discourse do relate with one another.

2.3 Extending the Application of Speech Acts Theory in the Present Study:

In applying speech acts theory to instances of language, Searle concentrates on isolated (and contrived) sentences. The present study attempts to extend the application of speech acts theory beyond isolated sentences to suprasentential stretches of language in actual usage; we do so in order to analyze sequences of speech acts within a discourse and to determine just how the speech acts contained in a discourse relate to one another. The argument for this extension of the application of speech acts theory to suprasentential stretches of language derives from the recognition of the fact that speech acts, rather than occurring in isolation in real life, normally come in sequences within a discourse, as is the case with public-service advertisements. Majority of the public-service advertisements in our corpus contain more than one speech act and the speech acts contract some form of relationship with one another such that they combine to produce some perlocutionary effects on the hearers.

Within the advertisements, there is usually a dominant speech act while the other(s) is (are) subordinate. This hierarchy (i.e., dominance-subordination order) is based on the intuitive notion of main point, such that the dominant speech act carries the main point while the subordinate speech act carries the sub-point, thus effectively contracting some kind of relationship one with the other. The status of the goal the speech acts are supposed to achieve determines the status (as main or subordinate) that the speech acts are assigned. The contextual background of the public-service advertisements with which we are concerned help to determine both the dominant and the subordinate speech acts in the sense that the dominant speech act will focus on the positive behaviour pattern that the advertisement emphasizes.

The speech acts evident in the public-service advertisements relate with one another on the basis of specified rules of relationship. However, the rules are not necessarily formulated on the basis of the sequential or linear order of speech acts;

rather, they are based on the main point of the sequence of speech acts contained in each public-service advertisement. As earlier mentioned, it is the contextual background of the public-service advertisements that helps to determine both the main point and the subordinate point. The speech act that contains the main point becomes the main speech act while that which carries the subordinate point becomes the subordinate speech act. It is the way subordinate speech acts interact with the main speech act that determines the type of relationship they contract with the main speech act. The rules of relationship incorporate Searle's criteria for classifying speech acts in such a way that the speech acts contained in the public-service advertisements are first of all identified and classified before the type of relationship they contract with one another can be specified. In other words, the determination of the type of relationship the speech acts contract with one another is dependent on the identification of the type of speech acts in question. This means in effect that the rules of relationship work hand-in-hand with Searle's criteria for classifying speech acts. The speech acts are identified on the basis of the three

major criteria for classifying them: (1) "illocutionary point or purpose", (2) "direction of fit between words and the world", and (3) "expressed psychological state" (cf. 2.1..2).

It is to be noted that the speech acts are delineated by message units. As earlier mentioned (c.f. 2. 1. 1.), each message unit expresses one complete identifiable point. Each complete point marks a speech act. Thus, we analyze the following public-service advertisement taken from our corpus:

Text 11

Think of what you will do for
your country and not what
your country will do for you.

as comprising two speech acts, though the speech acts are contained in one sentence. This is because it is evident that the text (ie, Text 11) consists of two complete identifiable points. The first point is: 'Think of what you will do for your country'

country" while the second point which is conjoined to the first point could read as follows: 'Do not think of what your country will do for you'. The speech acts being performed are both directives.

Having pointed out that speech acts are delineated by message units, let us consider another public-service advertisement taken from our corpus:

Text 35

It is a grave mistake to be involved in electoral offences. Refrain from them.

This illustrative public-service advertisement contains two message units which constitute two speech acts. The illocutionary point of the first speech act (i.e., 'It is a grave mistake to be involved in electoral offences'.) commits the speaker to "something's being the case, to the truth of the expressed proposition." It is true that involvement in electoral offences is a grave mistake because such offences usually attract punishment since there is a law against them. Its

direction of fit is 'words-to-the world': the words express what obtains. The expressed psychological state is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it too. Thus, this speech act is classified as an assertive. The criteria for identifying assertives are formalized as indicated on (section 2.1.2) and reproduced here for ease of reference:

$$\vdash \downarrow B(p)$$

(Where (i) $\vdash$ represents an assertion sign,
 (ii) $\downarrow$ the words-to-world direction of fit,
 (iii) B the sincerity condition of belief, and
 (iv) p the propositional content. (Searle, 1976:10).

It is to be noted that each time we find (i) through (iv) above, then we have an assertive speech act.

The illocutionary point of the second speech act (i.e., 'Refrain from them'.) is "to get the hearer to do something": in this case, to refrain from electoral offences - the pronoun them contained in the directive is anaphoric to 'electoral offences'

contained in the assertive speech act. The direction of fit of the speech act is world-to-words: the speaker tries to get reality to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state is wish: the speaker wishes that the hearers refrain from electoral offences. Thus, this speech act is classified as a directive. These criteria for identifying directives are formalized as indicated on (section 2.1.2) and reproduced here for ease of reference:

!↑ W(H does A)

(Where the exclamation mark represents the illocutionary point - indicating device for members of the directive class, the upward arrow represents the world-to-words direction of fit, and W represents the sincerity condition.)

Having identified and classified the two speech acts contained in **Text 35** above, we can then determine the type of relationship they contract with each another. These speech acts are ordered hierarchically, along a 'dominance - subordination

line' based on the intuitive notion of main point, such that the dominant speech act carries the main point while the subordinate speech act carries the sub-point, and the subordinate speech act, in effect, contracts a kind of relationship with the main speech act. Thus, in the above illustrative advertisement, the directive speech act (i.e., 'Refrain from them'.) is the dominant speech act while the assertive speech act (i.e., 'It is a grave mistake to be involved in electoral offences.')

is the subordinate speech act, and it contracts a relation of justification with the main speech act because the assertive speech act provides motivation for and justification for the directive speech act which carries the main point of the message of the advertisement. Thus, the assertive combines with the directive to help the speaker achieve his illocutionary goal which is causing a positive change in the attitude and behaviour pattern of the hearer(s).

However, the relationship of justification is not necessarily determined by the linear order of the speech acts, rather it is determined by the presence of a particular type of speech act

providing motivation or justification for another speech act which carries the main point of the discourse. Consider in this connection, the following public-service advertisement taken from our corpus:

Text 49

Political leaders should always think and programme well for the masses who vote them in.

Public office means public trust.

This text (**Text 49**) contains two speech acts corresponding to the two message units outlined above. The illocutionary point in the first speech act exhorts political leaders to map out good programme for the benefit of the people who gave them the mandate to govern. Its direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get political aspirants to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state is wish: the speaker wishes that political aspirants would care for the people they aspire to govern. The relevant speech act, therefore, fulfils conditions that identify directives. It is thus a directive speech act.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act (i.e., 'Public office means public trust'.) commits the speaker to the truth of the expressed proposition: it is true that the people repose some measure of confidence in the political leaders they vote into office in a way that demands responsibility from the political leaders towards the people. The direction of fit of the speech act is words-to-world: the words express the status quo. The expressed psychological state is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it as well. This speech act, therefore, satisfies conditions that identify assertives. It is thus an assertive speech.

The assertive speech act in the text under consideration (**Text 49**) defines the premise from which the preceding directive flows. It provides the necessary justification for the directive. The directive carries the main point of the advertisement. The illocutionary goal of the directive is to get political

aspirants to come up with programmes that will be of benefit to the people they aspire to govern. Thus, the directive is the main speech act in the sequence.

However, unlike the sequential order evident in **Text 35** where the assertive speech act comes before the directive speech act, the sequential order in **Text 49** is such that the directive comes before the assertive, but in spite of the difference in their ordering, the assertive speech acts in each of **Text 35** and **Text 49** contract a relationship of justification with the directive speech acts.

An analysis of the speech acts evident in the public-service advertisements in our corpus, shows that in most cases, the assertives come before the directives whenever they contract a relationship of justification. This may be because it is probably more polite for the reasons motivating the directive to precede the directive. The hearer(s) is / (are) better prepared to receive the directive when the justification for the directive is clearly articulated.

A rule to account for the relation of justification can, in the circumstances, be formulated thus:

Rule 1

A speech act SA_1 stands in a relationship of justification with another speech act SA_2 if, and only if, SA_1 and SA_2 are non-identical speech act types such that SA_1 provides the justification for SA_2 , where SA_1 and SA_2 are not necessarily linearly ordered.

Formalization of Rule 1:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} SA_1 \xrightarrow{J} SA_2 \\ SA_2 \xleftarrow{J} SA_1 \end{array} \right\} \text{iff } SA_1 \text{ typologically } \neq SA_2$$

& $(\forall SA) (SA_1 \xrightarrow{J} SA_2 \supset SA_1 \text{ provides the justification for } SA_2.)$

(Where $\xrightarrow{J}$ means justifies; iff symbolizes if, and only if; $\neq$ symbolizes non-identical; & symbolizes and; $\forall$ is the universal quantifier symbol in symbolic logic; $\supset$ symbolizes logically implies/means.)

The relation of justification is just one of the types of relationships identified in our corpus. The other types of relationships are discussed in the immediately following chapter. The chapter presents the speech acts analysis of the data with which the study is concerned. All our rules of relationship will take the form of specifying the environment in which speech acts contract particular types of relationships as shown in the above example with the relationship of justification.

CHAPTER THREE

SPEECH ACTS IN THE PUBLIC-SERVICE ADVERTISEMENTS: APPLICATION OF THEORY

3.1 SAMPLE ANALYSIS:

The public-service advertisements in our corpus are classified under three main categories, namely: SAP-related advertisements, MAMSER-related advertisements and advertisements related to Political Education. The classification is based on the particular aspect of the mobilization programme emphasized or focused in particular advertisements. Although all the public-service advertisements examined share a macro-context, that is, mobilization towards a new socio-economic and political order in Nigeria, they also have micro-contexts. The micro-contexts are the various foci of the mobilization process which can be economic, social, or political. Thus, the micro-context of the SAP-related advertisements is economic mobilization, that of the MAMSER-related advertisements is

social mobilization while that of the advertisements related to Political Education is political mobilization.

A total of fifty public-service advertisements make up the corpus of this study. They comprise six SAP-related advertisements, thirteen MAMSER-related advertisements and thirty-one advertisements related to the Political Education Programme.

The present writer collected more political education-related advertisements than any other type because the advertisements were recorded between 1989 and 1991, i.e., at the time when the two political parties formed by the Federal Military Government (i.e, Social Democratic Party (SDP) and National Republican Convention (NRC) were being ushered in and the period the governorship elections were being conducted and more public-service advertisements focused on the political education programme were put out on radio and the media generally.

An analysis of illustrations of the different kinds of speech acts evident in the three categories of public-service advertisements is provided below to show what sets each class of speech acts apart from the other.

SAP-related advertisements:

Text 1

Farming has always been a noble profession in our land. It will even be worthier to farm in these days of self-reliance. Let us go back to the land and make Nigeria grow.

This advertisement contains four speech acts corresponding to the four message units outlined above. The illocutionary point in 'Farming has always been a noble profession in our land'., is to ascribe a particular value rating to the practice of farming as a profession in Nigeria. From the contextual background to the SAP-related advertisements (cf. Chapter One: 1.5.1), it

will be recalled that before the oil boom era, the greater percentage of government revenue accrued from the agricultural sector. Although there do not appear to have been large extensively mechanized farms around, farming was obviously a major occupation among rural dwellers and farmers were most certainly not looked down on. Unfortunately, however, with the discovery of crude oil in commercial quantities, the focus of government shifted so much in the 1970's to the oil sector that agriculture was neglected during the oil boom era. The money that accrued during this period of oil boom was invested in the provision of social, physical, and economic infrastructures, largely in the urban areas and at the expense of the rural areas. The result is that many Nigerians abandoned the farms for other jobs in the urban areas. Thus, the proposition of the relevant speech act is true of the pre-oil boom era in Nigeria. Its direction of fit is words to the world. The words tells us the status of farming at a given period in Nigeria. The expressed psychological state is belief: the speaker believes the proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it too. The

speech act concerned therefore fulfils the conditions that identify assertives. (cf. Chapter Two: 2.1. 2.)

The illocutionary point in the second speech act (i.e., 'It will even be worthier to farm in these days of self-reliance'), boils down to insistence that farming is even more relevant to the move towards self-reliance in Nigeria than many may realize. Considering the context of this advertisement (i.e., economic recovery), government's conclusion appears to be that total dependence on petroleum is ruinous and dangerous for the economy and wishes the citizenry to recognize this and then see farming as another source of improving the economy. Thus, its direction of fit is words to the world. The expressed psychological state is belief(that p). This speech act also fulfils the conditions that identify assertives, thus it is an assertive speech act.

The third speech act in the above advertisement is 'Let us go back to the land'. The illocutionary point is to get as many people as possible to embrace farming in order to improve

production levels in the agricultural sector to achieve self-sufficiency in food production and also increase agricultural export produce via higher yield, so that the economy will not depend solely on petroleum as the major export produce. The direction of fit of the expressed proposition is world-to-the words: for many more Nigerians to engage in farming. The expressed psychological state of this speech act is desire: that farming becomes largely embraced in different dimensions. We are, therefore, clearly faced with a directive speech act.

The last speech act is conjoined with the third speech act by a coordinating conjunction and. It could read as: 'and let us make Nigeria grow'. The illocutionary point of this speech act is to get Nigerians to contribute to the economic growth of Nigeria. The Structural Adjustment Programme is geared towards achieving economic growth for Nigeria and every Nigerian is called to be part of the economic recovery of the country. One way to guarantee this, as earlier mentioned, is for many more Nigerians to engage in farming. The direction of fit of the expressed proposition is world-to-the words: for Nigeria

to grow. The expressed psychological state of this speech act is desire: Nigeria's growth. In this regard, we are presented with a directive speech act.

MAMSER-related advertisement:

Text 12

Hoarders of essential commodities are
enemies of the society.

Expose them.

In this advertisement, we have two speech acts. The illocutionary point in the first speech act (i.e., 'Hoarders of essential commodities are enemies of the society'.) is the message that hoarding is harmful to society because it brings about artificial scarcity which results in inflation. Those who engage in hoarding must therefore be seen as enemies of the society. In Nigeria, there are people who hoard goods, particularly those goods classified as essential commodities such as rice, vegetable oil, etc. (especially during festive periods). Thus, it is part of the shared background knowledge of Nigerians that there is

scarcity of essential commodities coupled with diabolically high prices. The direction of fit of this speech act is words to the world: the words described the status quo. The expressed psychological state is belief: the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it too. The speech act thus satisfies the conditions that identify assertives.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act (i.e., 'Expose them'.) is to get the hearers to understand the necessity to deal with the problem posed by hoarders by cooperating with government, since they can only be dealt with if they are exposed to the appropriate agencies of government. This also happens to coincide with the propositional content of the relevant speech act. Its direction of fit is world to words: the society has to be rid of hoarders; exposing them will help curb their nefarious activities. The expressed psychological state is desire for change. We are, as it were, presented with a directive speech act.

Political Education advertisement:**Text 41**

Do not sell your votes. They form part of your weapons to install a good government in the country.

The above advertisement contains two speech acts. The illocutionary point in the first speech act is general exhortation not to sell one's votes. Its propositional content is that a voter's card has to be seen as a prized possession of any responsible citizen desirous of seeing the installation of a responsive government. It must not be exchanged for anything. The relevance of this exhortation arises from the fact that past elections were known to have been characterized by large scale electoral malpractices including cash inducements. The incidence of large scale electoral malpractices forms part of the shared background knowledge of Nigerians. The direction of fit of the speech act is world-to-words, that is, the realities around us all should reflect changes in previous patterns of behaviour vis-a-vis elections and attitudes to the voter's card.

The expressed psychological state of the speech act is desire for political consciousness. The relevant speech act, therefore, meets the conditions that identify directives.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act (i.e., 'They form part of your weapons to install a good government in the country'.) is to emphasize the importance of the vote as an instrument in the drive to install a caring, responsive government. Its direction of fit is words to the world: the citizenry determines the kind of government it gets by what it does with its civic responsibilities such as voting. The voter's card is, therefore, part of the armoury in the 'battle' to secure a good government. The expressed psychological state is belief: the success of the political education programme hinges on recognition of a number of facts on the part of the citizenry. The speech act concerned, therefore, fulfils the conditions that identify assertives.

The foregoing analysis of the speech acts in the three texts of public-service advertisements shows that the illocutionary

point, the direction of fit and the expressed psychological state (ie, the sincerity condition) are the factors that set each class of speech acts apart from the other. The propositional content of the speech acts reflects the focus of the public-service advertisements, that is, whether they deal with economic, social, or political mobilization.

3.2 Speech Act Types in the Public-Service Advertisements:

The public-service advertisements in our corpus were analysed as shown in the sample analysis above. An examination of the data reveals that Assertives and Directives are the predominant types of speech acts used in the public-service advertisements. (see Appendix for the data). There was no instance of Commissives, Expressives and Declarations in any of the advertisements, thus suggesting that these speech act types may not be effective in achieving the goals of a mass mobilization programme.

We find that 75.4% of the total speech acts involved in the SAP-related advertisements are assertives while only 24.6% are directives. (See the appendix.) The dominance of assertives is very significant indeed. One explanation for the high incidence of assertives may well be that Nigerians need to be encouraged to cope with the hard times arising from the Structural Adjustment Programme. Encouragement and/or prodding sits well with assertives expressing/describing the new values to be embraced, or at least presenting them in terms that can compel compliance or adoption. Considering that assertives tend to assert/express commitment to 'something's being the case', their widespread use does seem understandable. The point to note here is that assertives have truth values which enhance the compelling effect of the asserted propositions. It is in this sense that the assertives identified in the preceding analysis invariably provide motivation for the directives.

The MAMSER-related advertisements for their part consist of 33.3% assertives and 66.7% directives. To the extent

that the main task of the Social Mobilization Programme is to create national awareness and bring about positive changes in the general attitude of Nigerians, it is no surprise that directive type of speech acts are the predominant group in this category of public-service advertisements.

The public-service advertisements related to the Political Education Programme, however, consist of 54.4% assertives and 45.6% directives. The higher use of assertives may be because a large proportion of Nigerians need to be enlightened on what installing a democratic government entails in order for them to appreciate as well as carry out the directives. The basis for assuming that enlightenment is called for to ensure that the people are not swindled into "selling their birthright for a mess of pottage," as it were, by the political and educated elite is because the realities of past experiences with politics in Nigeria reveal a need for change in the right direction.

On the whole, the public-service advertisements in our data consist of 57.0% assertives and 43.0% directives.

3.3 Speech Act Sequences in the Public-Service Advertisements:

Speech acts do not normally occur in isolation in real life; rather they come in sequences within a discourse. Such sequential speech acts are also normally related to one another, one way or the other, although they tend to point to status differentials in 'the flow of the speaker's action' as will become clear in what follows. Consider, therefore, the following public-service advertisements:

Text 34

A good and responsible government
does not come by chance. Vote sensibly
to ensure this.

This public-service advertisement contains two speech acts corresponding to the two message units outlined above. The illocutionary point in the first speech act is to inform the people that a good and responsible government does not come by chance: they need to work hard to bring it about. Its direction

of fit is words to world: the citizenry determines the kind of government it gets by how it responds to processes that bring about the government. The expressed psychological state is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it too. The relevant speech act, therefore, fulfils the conditions that identify assertives. It is, thus, an assertive speech act.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act (i.e., 'Vote sensibly to ensure this.') is to exhort the people to vote wisely as a guarantee for securing a good government. The direction of fit of the speech act is world-to-words, that is, it is only through judicious voting that we can get a good and responsible government. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is desire for prudent voting. In this regard, we are clearly faced with a directive speech act.

With the identification of the types of speech acts that characterize the public-service advertisement under consideration (**Text 34**), we can then discuss how the speech acts

relate to one another. The assertive and directive speech acts evident in this public-service advertisement do not occur at the same level, rather they are ordered hierarchically, along a dominance - subordination line based on the intuitive notion of main point. The main goal of the public-service advertisement in question is to ensure that Nigerians vote for the right candidates while the sub-goal is to provide good justification for the advice outlined in the advertisement - this is done via an expression indicating commitment 'to something's being the case' (i.e., 'A good and responsible government does not come by chance.') The claim that a good and responsible government does not come by chance, therefore, is the basis for the advice that follows. The main point of the sequence is contained in the directive such that the assertive is merely a supportive device providing motivation for the main act. As main act, the directive dominates the illocutionary goal. The assertive, though a subordinate act, contributes to the achievement of the main goal by providing a sufficiently compelling reason for, or one that is at least capable of inducing compliance with the directive. The realization of the main goal is, of

course, the perlocutionary intention.

The relationship between the speech acts in **Text 34** is one of justification. The desired effect of justification is that of providing the motivation/reason for giving the directive in order to enhance compliance. This is to say that the subordinate acts must be relevant to the main act and the reasons provided must be plausible enough to achieve the designs of the main act.

Let us consider another public-service advertisement below:

Text 50

Ai wọn bi ọga, i izi fọ tọk.

If yu wọn bi bẹta ọga,

Opun yọ iẹ, hiẹ yọ pipul o!

Na dẹm put yu dẹ o!

Text 50 is a public-service advertisement in Nigerian Pidgin. It contains three message units which constitute three speech

acts. The illocutionary point in the first speech act (i.e., ‘Ai wọn bi ọga, i izi fọ tok’.) commits the speaker to “something’s being the case, to the truth of the expressed proposition.” It is true that it is easy for one to express the wish to be a leader - the reality of being a leader is a different ball game altogether. Its direction of fit is words-to-the-world: the words express what obtains. The expressed psychological state is belief(that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it too. This speech act, therefore, satisfies the conditions that identify assertives.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act (i.e., ‘If yu wọn be bẹta ọga, opun yọ iẹ, hiẹ yọ pipul o!’) is to advise political aspirants on how to be good leaders: it exhorts that those who aspire to be good leaders must listen to those they aspire to lead. The direction of fit of this speech act is world-to-words: the speaker tries to get political aspirants to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state is wish: the speaker wishes the political aspirants to be responsive to the people they aspire to govern. In this connection, we are

presented with a directive speech act.

The illocutionary point in the third speech act (i.e., 'Na dem pu yu de o!') explains that it is the people that gave the political aspirants the mandate to govern them. The direction of fit of this speech act is words-to-world: the words express the status quo. The expressed psychological state is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it as well. We are, therefore, faced with an assertive speech act.

Essentially, **Text 50** contains two assertive speech acts and one directive speech act. The directive is placed in-between the assertives. The first assertive provides the motivation for the directive. The goal of the directive is to get political aspirants to appreciate what it takes to be responsible, responsive and worthy leaders. This message of the directive is, thus, the main point of the sequence. The result is that the directive is the main speech act in the sequence. The second assertive (i.e., 'Na dem put yu de o!') provides the necessary justification for the directive and the necessity for political

aspirants to follow the advice proffered since it is the people that give political aspirants the mandate to govern them by voting them into office. The leaders should therefore not neglect or oppress the people. The second assertive, therefore, contributes to the achievement of the main goal by providing a basis for the advice that is likely to appeal to the good sense of political aspirants who do not wish to commit professional suicide.

As subordinate acts, the two assertives have goals that are sub-goals. Both are relevant to the main act and contract a justification relation with their directive counterpart, i.e., 'If you wɔn bi beta ɔga opun yɔ ie, hiɛ yɔ pipul o!' The first assertive sounds a warning that prepares the ground for the directive and combines with the second assertive to provide whatever motivation is required for the latter and thus enhances the chances of compliance with the directive by the target audience.

Another example of public-service advertisements in our

data containing speech act sequences that have a relation of justification is given below:

Text 4

Hard times are here but not forever.

Everyone has got a dream.

You've got yours and I've got mine.

What it takes is guts and sacrifice to pull this country through, or your dreams will fade away. Yea, what it takes is guts and sacrifice to pull this country through. Hard times are like bad dreams, but they don't last forever.

Don't despair.

This public-service advertisement contains eleven speech acts in all. The illocutionary point in the first speech act (ie, 'Hard times are here') is to assert, as it were, the present reality of life in Nigeria, as a way of expressing knowledge of what the people are experiencing. Its direction of fit is words-to-the

world: the words tell us what obtains-it is the case that Nigerians are going through hard times. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is belief (that p): the speaker believe the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it too. In this connection, we are presented with an assertive speech act.

The second speech act is conjoined with the first speech act by a contrasting conjunction but. The illocutionary point in the second speech act (i.e., 'but not forever') is to reassure Nigerians and rekindle their faith in the future by reminding them that the hard times arising from the Structural Adjustment Programme will not last forever. Its direction of fit is words-to-the world: the words tell us that the hard times are transitory. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it too. In this regard, we are faced with an assertive speech act.

The illocutionary points in the third, fourth and fifth speech acts remind the people that they have dreams which they would most certainly wish to see actualized. Their direc-

tion of fit is words-to-world: The words tell us what prevails - it is the case that everyone has get a dream. Their expressed psychological state is belief (that p). These speech acts, therefore, fulfil conditions that identify assertives.

The illocutionary points in the sixth, seventh and eight speech acts explain that the possibility of realizing such dreams will depend largely on today's sacrifice. Their direction of fit is words-to-the world: the words tell us what obtains - generally, we make some sacrifices in order to realize our dreams. The expressed psychological state of the speech acts is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it as well. We are, therefore, presented with assertive speech acts.

The illocutionary points in the ninth and tenth speech acts re-echo the illocutionary points in the first and second speech acts as a way of emphasizing them: they give the people the hope that the hard times will cease sometime in the future, thus,

encouraging the people to cope as best as they can with the hardship they are experiencing. The direction of fit of the speech act is also words-to-the world: just as the first speech act, the words tell us that the hard times will pass away. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is also belief (that p). This speech act also fulfils conditions that identify assertives.

The illocutionary point in the eleventh speech act exhorts the people not to despair. Its direction of fit is world-to-words: the speaker tries to get the hearers not to lose hope since the hard times will not last forever. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is wish: the speaker wishes the hearers to be hopeful. This speech act, therefore, fulfils conditions that identify directives. It is thus a directive speech act.

Essentially, the above assertives together form the basis for the directive (i.e., 'Don't despair.'). The main point of the sequence is contained in the directive. It is the dominant illocutionary goal while the assertives are the subordinate goals providing motivation for the directive. The assertives

combine to encourage the people not to despair.

The above analysis, however, raises an important issue: the issue of interpreting relations between multiple instances of speech acts sequences contained in one text where such speech acts clusters have the same goal as evident in Text 4 above. The question is whether in assigning relationship types to such speech act sequences, we should regard speech acts that share the same goal as single speech acts and, thus, treat them as independent entities or whether we should, as we have done above, simply regard them as speech act clusters which have the same goal and can therefore be treated as one group. The resolution of the issues involved in the question raised here will have to await future research on the subject.

The present analysis shows that whenever assertives and directives occur within the same public-service advertisement, the assertives regularly contract a relationship of Justification with the directives.

A rule to account for the relation of justification, in the circumstances, can be formulated as indicated on (section 2.3) and reproduced here for ease of reference:

Rule 1

A speech act SA_1 stands in a relationship of justification with another speech act SA_2 if, and only if, SA_1 and SA_2 are non-identical speech act types such that SA_1 provides the justification for SA_2 , where SA_1 and SA_2 are not necessarily linearly ordered.

Formalization of Rule 1:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} SA_1 \xrightarrow{J} SA_2 \\ SA_2 \xleftarrow{J} SA_1 \end{array} \right\} \text{iff } SA_1 \text{ typologically } \neq SA_2$$

$\&(\text{USA}) (SA_1 \xrightarrow{J} SA_2 \supset SA_1 \text{ provides the justification for } SA_2.)$

(Where $\xrightarrow{J}$ means justify; iff symbolizes if, and only if; $\neq$ symbolizes non-identical; $\&$ symbolizes and; $\forall$ is the universal quantifier symbol in symbolic logic; $\supset$ symbolizes logically implies/means.)

Two other types of relations are found in the speech act sequences identified in some of the public-service advertise-

ments in our data. These are a relation of amplification and a relation of contrastive apposition. Consider in this connection the following public-service advertisements:

Text 30

Be committed to the return of democracy. Don't hinder the implementation of the transition programme.

Text 30 contains two speech acts. The message of this public-service advertisement is that some group of Nigerians obviously want to undermine or even distract attention from the implementation of the transition to civil rule programme and that that is not in anyone's long term interest. Thus, the illocutionary point in the first speech act is to enjoin Nigerians to support and be committed to the return to democratic government. Its direction of fit is world-to-words: the speaker tries to get Nigerians to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state is desire: the speaker desires that Nigerians become committed to the return to democracy. In this regard, we are presented with a directive speech act.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act exhorts Nigerians not to hinder the implementation of the transition programme. Its direction of fit is also world-to-words: the speaker tries to get Nigerians to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state is desire: the speaker desires that Nigerians do not hinder the implementation of the transition programme. We are, therefore, faced with another directive speech act.

Ultimately, both the first and second directive speech acts aim at achieving commitment to a specified programme: political transition programme. However, the first directive carries the main point of the advertisement: it enjoins Nigerians to support and be committed to the return to democratic government. The second directive, on the other hand, outlines just how to demonstrate the required commitments, that is by not doing anything to obstruct the smooth implementation of the political transition programme. In other words, the second directive specifies what would boil down to heeding the counsel of the first directive. Thus, the second directive

contracts a relationship of amplification with the first directive.

Text 9

Be a good Nigerian.

Buy home-made goods.

Text 9 comprises two speech acts. The illocutionary point in the first speech act is to exhort Nigerians to be good citizens. Its direction of fit is world-to-words: the speaker tries to get Nigerians to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state is desire: desire for Nigerians to be good citizens. Thus, this speech act fulfils the conditions that identify directive speech acts. It is, therefore, a directive speech act.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act is to exhort Nigerians to buy goods produced in Nigeria. Its direction of fit is also world-to-words: the speaker tries to get Nigerians to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state is desire: desire for Nigerians to buy home-made goods. We are, therefore, clearly faced with a directive speech act.

Fundamentally, the first and second directives together insist that good citizens usually buy locally produced goods. First, we are told in the first directive to be good citizens. By telling Nigerians to buy home-made goods in the immediately following sequence represented by the second directive, it is assumed that the target audience will make the logical inference that buying locally made goods is one way, at least, of demonstrating that one is a good citizen. Thus, the second directive contracts a relation of amplification with the first directive in the sense that it outlines what would amount to heeding the counsel of the first directive. The first directive carries the main point of the advertisement which the second directive amplifies

Text 27

Social Democratic Party (SDP), National
 Republican Convention (NRC),
 di tu pati we govm̄nt apruv na wi on.
 B-a-b-a ke! no de f̄o dis w̄on at ọl.
 Evrib̄odi na ikūọl m̄emba o!

Text 27 consists of three speech acts which are in Nigerian Pidgin. The illocutionary point in the first speech act tells us that SDP and NRC are the two political parties approved by the government for all Nigerians. Its direction of fit is words-to-world: the Federal Military Government formed the two parties for the benefit of all who are interested to join. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it too. This speech act, therefore, satisfies the conditions that identify assertives.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act (i.e., 'B-a-b-a ke! no de fo dis won at ol.') explains that this time around, no individual politician can claim to be the founder/leader of any of the parties or legitimately be so considered. Its direction of fit is words-to-world: the words express the reality of the formation of the two political parties. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it too. Thus, this speech act fulfils the conditions that identify assertives.

The illocutionary point in the third speech act (i.e., *Èvribòdi na ikuòl mèm̄ba o!*) tells us that everybody who becomes a member of any of the two political parties is an equal member since all members are equal joiners, as it were. Its direction of fit is words-to-the-world; the words express what obtains. The expressed psychological state is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it as well. We are, therefore, presented with an assertive speech act.

The first assertive speech act in this Text 27 carries the main point of the public-service advertisement: it tells us that the two parties are collectively owned by all Nigerians. The second assertive (i.e., *'B-a-b-a kẹ! no de fọ dis wọn at ọ!*') explains the propositional content of the first assertive, that is, that no politician has the moral right to claim superior membership because the parties *'na wi on'* (are ours), the two parties belong to all Nigerians. The third assertive (i.e., *'Èvribòdi na*

ikuql memba o!') clarifies the propositional content of the second assertive by explaining that everybody is an equal member in the sense that the Federal Military Government formed the two parties for the benefit of all who are interested to join to ensure that no party member is subordinate to the other. Thus, the third assertive contracts a relation of amplification with the second assertive and, similarly, the second assertive contracts a relation of amplification with the first assertive.

It is interesting to note that there is no mixing of speech acts when they are in a relationship of amplification. This is clearly in direct contrast with the situation in sequences mediated by a relation of justification where speech acts of different kinds tend to co-occur. In other words, when a public-service advertisement is made up of sequences of speech acts in a relationship that can be termed amplification, the speech acts must be of an identical kind. Put differently, we would say only identical sequences of speech acts can occur in a relation of amplification such that either the public-service advertise-

ment contains only directive speech acts (as in Texts 30 and 9) or only assertive speech acts (as in Text 27).

The following rule attempts to capture the special features characterizing the relation of amplification.

Rule 2

A speech act SA_1 stands in a relationship of amplification with another speech act SA_2 if, and only if, SA_1 and SA_2 are identical speech act type such that SA_2 amplifies the proposition expressed by SA_1 .

Formalization of Rule 2:

$SA_1 \leftarrow^A SA_2$ iff SA_1 typologically = SA_2
& $(\forall SA) (SA_1 \leftarrow^A SA_2 \supset SA_2$ amplifies the proposition expressed by SA_1 .)

(where $\leftarrow^A$ means amplifies; iff symbolizes if, and only if; = symbolizes identical; & symbolizes and; $\forall$ is the universal quantifier symbol in symbolic logic; $\supset$ symbolizes logically implies/means.)

As mentioned earlier, some of the public-service advertisements contain speech act sequences mediated by a relation

of contrastive apposition. Consider, in this connection, the following public-service advertisement:

Text 10

Say no to bribery and corruption. Say no to drug-abuse and trafficking. Say no to idleness. But, yes to uprightness. Yes to diligence. And, yes to nationalism and patriotism.

The above public-service advertisement (Text 10) contains six speech acts in all. The illocutionary points in the first three speech acts draw attention to behaviour patterns that must be jettisoned: bribery and corruption, drug-abuse and trafficking, and idleness. Their direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get the hearers to give up negative behaviour patterns. The expressed psychological state of the speech acts is desire: that Nigerians eschew vices. These speech acts, therefore, fulfil conditions that identify directives. Thus, the first three speech acts are directive speech acts.

The illocutionary points in the last three speech acts, on the contrary, highlight more wholesome, edifying and generally more rewarding attributes and attitudes worth cultivating, namely, uprightness, diligence, nationalism and patriotism. Their direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get the hearers to uphold positive behaviour patterns. Their expressed psychological state is desire: that Nigerians take steps in the right direction. These speech acts, therefore, fulfil conditions that identify directive speech acts. Thus, the last three speech acts are also directives.

The first three directives, as it were, condemn the indiscipline inherent in prevalent behaviour patterns and attitudes while the last three directives draw attention to the path likely to lead to the well-being of everyone. In essence, the last three directives provide some contrasting positive behaviour patterns as alternatives for those condemned by the first three directives. In this regard, the last three directives together constitute the main point of the advertisement since they provide positive choices for the people. Thus, the first three

directives contract a relationship of contrastive apposition with the last three directives.

The above **Text 10** is another instance where we have speech acts clusters which have the same goal; the first three speech acts have the same goal while the last three speech acts also have the same goal.

Text 14

Don't merely preach what is good for the society. Show it by example.

Text 14 consists of two speech acts. The illocutionary point in the first speech act (i.e., 'Don't merely preach what is good for the society.') exhorts the leaders themselves and the society at large that they should not only point out what should obtain in the society. Its direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get the hearers to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is desire: the speaker desires that the hearers should not be mere preachers of good standard for the society. This speech act, therefore,

fulfils conditions that identify directives.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act (i.e., 'Show it by example.') exhorts the people to practice what they preach. Its direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get the hearers to conform to his words. Its expressed psychological state is desire: the speaker desires that the hearers should lead by example. In this regard, we are faced with a directive speech act.

Essentially, the second directive provides a contrasting positive behaviour pattern by specifying the right thing to do, that is, those who talk about what is right and what should be done in the society, should also put their own exhortation into practice. In other words, the citizenry is being exhorted to be consistent by only asking one of the other only that which each can ask of himself. Thus, the second directive contracts a relationship of contrastive apposition with the first directive. Moreover, the second directive contains the main point of the advertisement.

Text 2

When we depend on government to employ everybody, then we are not being realistic. But, when we engage in self-employment, then we are being realistic.

And, that is the sense in SAP.

Text 2 comprises three speech acts. The illocutionary point in the first speech act specifies what can pass for not being realistic. Its direction of fit is words-to-the world: the words express the reality of the employment situation in Nigeria today - the government cannot employ everyone. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearers to believe it too. This speech act, therefore, satisfies the conditions that identify assertives.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act specifies what being realistic would boil down to. Its direction of fit is words-to-the world: the words express what is the case - it is

the case that engaging in self-employment amounts to being realistic in the present circumstances in Nigeria's job market. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearers to believe it as well. We are, therefore, presented with an assertive speech act.

The illocutionary point in the third speech act tells us that SAP (i.e., Structural Adjustment Programme) is designed to get more Nigerians to opt for being realistic. The that contained in this speech act has the compound word 'self-employment' contained in the second speech act as antecedent. Thus, this third speech act implies that Nigerians should consider the possibility of minimizing their dependence on government by embracing self-employment since it is self-evident that government cannot employ everybody. Its direction of fit is words-to-world: the words express what is the case - it is the case that SAP is intended to encourage self-reliance. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the

hearers to believe it too. Thus, this speech act fulfils the conditions that identify assertives.

The above **Text 2**, as it were, contains three assertive speech acts. The proposition expressed by the second assertive above contracts a relation of contrastive apposition with the first assertive. The second assertive also provides the reference point for the third assertive. The third assertive, in addition, combines with the second assertive to contract a relation of contrastive apposition with the first assertive. However, the third assertive with reference to the point of the second assertive, contains the main point of the public-service advertisement, that is to provide one of the reasons for the adoption of the Structural Adjustment Programme which is getting people to act realistically.

Just as with the relation of amplification, there is no mixing of speech acts when they are in a relation of contrastive apposition, rather, only typologically identical sequences of speech acts occur such that either the public-service advertise-

ment contains only directive speech acts (as in **Texts 10 and 14**) or only assertive speech acts (as in **Text 2**). However, the interaction of speech acts evident in the public-service advertisements distinguishes the relation of amplification from the relation of contrastive apposition. In other words, with speech acts mediated by a relation of amplification, the one amplifies the other. This means that the second speech act outlines what kind of behaviour can pass for heeding the counsel described by the first one. On the other hand, with speech acts mediated by a relation of contrastive apposition, we find a list of imperatives involving negation and referring to what can easily be described as unwholesome choices placed side by side, as it were, with imperatives without negation referring to more wholesome choices that people can make instead. The idea seems to be one of outlining contrasting choices via parallel structures such that the point of the message lies somewhere in the contrasts made between the different choices.

The following rule attempts to capture the special features characterizing the relation of contrastive apposition:

Rule 3

A speech act SA_1 stands in a relationship of contrastive apposition with another speech act SA_2 if, and only if, SA_1 and SA_2 are identical speech act types such that SA_2 provides contrasting positive behaviour pattern in apposition to that expressed by SA_1 .

Formalization of Rule 3:

$$SA_1 \overset{CA}{\leftarrow} SA_2 \text{ iff } SA_1 \text{ typologically} = SA_2$$

$$\& (\forall SA_1 \overset{CA}{\leftarrow} SA_2 \supset SA_2$$

provides contrasting positive behaviour

pattern in apposition to that expressed by SA_1 .)

(Where $\overset{CA}{\leftarrow}$ means contrastive apposition; iff symbolizes if, and only if; = symbolizes identical; & symbolizes and; $\forall$ is the universal quantifier symbol in symbolic logic;

$\supset$ symbolizes logically implies/means.)

It is interesting to note that some texts in our data contain more than one type of relationship between the speech acts. However, each type of relationship in such multiple cases still follow the same rule that pertains to its type. In this connection, let us consider the following public-service advertisement:

Text 32

Nigeria is one. Forget tribalism and be tolerant. Let us all join hands to lead Nigeria to greatness in the third republic.

This public-service advertisement contains four message units which constitute four speech acts. The illocutionary point in the first speech act (i.e., 'Nigeria is one'.) is to assert that though there are diverse ethnic groups in Nigeria, these different groups make up one country: Nigeria. The direction of fit of this speech act is words-to-the world: the words express the status quo. The expressed psychological state is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearer to believe it as well. We are, therefore, faced with an assertive speech act.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act (i.e., 'Forget tribalism') exhorts Nigerians to jettison tribalism. Its direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get the hearers to give up negative behaviour pattern. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is desire: that Nigerians eschew tribalism. This speech act, therefore, fulfils conditions that identify directives. Thus, it is a directive speech act.

The illocutionary point in the third speech act (i.e., 'be tolerant'), on the contrary, specifies the positive thing to do: Nigerians are asked to tolerate one another. Its direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get the hearers to →

uphold positive behaviour pattern. Its expressed psychological state is desire: that Nigerians should take the right step. We are, therefore, faced with a directive speech act.

The illocutionary point in the fourth speech act (i.e., 'Let us all join hands to lead Nigeria to greatness in the third republic'.) exhorts Nigerians to co-operate with one another in order to make Nigeria a great nation. Its direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get the hearers to conform to his words. Its expressed psychological state is desire: the speaker desires that the hearers co-operate with one another. In this regard, we are faced with a directive speech act.

Essentially, the first speech act contracts a relationship of justification with both the second and the third speech acts because it (i.e., the first speech act) provides the basis for the directives (i.e., the second and the third speech acts). The second speech act, on its part, contracts a relationship of contrastive apposition with the third speech act which constitutes the main point of the advertisement since it provides the positive choice for the people. The fourth speech act contracts a relationship of amplification with the third speech act in the sense that it outlines what would amount to heeding the counsel of the third speech act.

Thus, **Text 32** above contains the three types of relationships discussed in this work, namely, the relationships of justification, amplification, and contrastive apposition. This

configuration could be said to be a case of complex speech act sequencing.

One point that has to be emphasized is that a few of the public-service advertisements in our data are made up of single speech acts occurring in isolation, as it were. Two public-service advertisements are provided below as illustrations of this restricted set:

Text 18

As you step out today, put your nation
first.

This public-service advertisement contains only one speech act. The illocutionary point in the speech act exhorts Nigerians to be patriotic. Its direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get the hearers to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is desire: the speaker desires that Nigerians should love their country. This speech act, therefore, fulfils conditions that identify directives. It is, thus, a directive speech act.

Text 24

In the nineties and beyond, let us resolve to make Nigeria a better place.

Just as **Text 18** above, **Text 24** also contains one speech act. The illocutionary point in the speech act exhorts Nigerians to put in their best into building up the nation to make it a better place for all. Its direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get the hearers to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is desire: that Nigeria becomes a better place. In this connection, we are clearly faced with a directive speech act.

Such simple speech acts occurring in isolation tend not to involve as much specificity as their structurally more complex counterparts. In that sense they can be said to be essentially vague and generalised as to particular behaviour almost as if they make the assumption that Nigerians all know what would be best for their country across the board and are simply being exhorted to act in line with that knowledge. This much is clear anyway when they (ie., **Texts 18 and 24**) are placed side by side

anyway when they (ie., Texts 18 and 24) are placed side by side with any of Texts 1, 2, 4, 9, 10, 14, 27, 30, 50 and others, which are more explicit from the point of view of desired changes.

Generally, we find that, 50.9% of the public-service advertisements in our data contain speech act sequences that are in a relation of justification, 25.4% contain speech act sequences in a relation of amplification, 18.6% consist of speech act sequences in a relation of contrastive apposition, while the remaining 5.1% of the public-service advertisements are made up of single unit speech acts. The predominance of the relation of justification may simply derive from the fact that specifying some kind of justification for a directive endows it with a measure of legitimacy that stands a good chance of guaranteeing acceptability, and by extension, compliance.

3.4 MACRO-SPEECH ACT IN THE PUBLIC-SERVICE ADVERTISEMENTS:

Van Dijk (1977:232) defines macro-speech act as:

the global speech act performed by the utterance of a whole discourse, and executed by a sequence of possibly different speech acts.

The concept of Macro-speech act is concerned with the overall structure of communicative interaction. Speech act sequences, on the other hand, centre around the linear structure of speech acts (i.e, their micro-pragmatics).

In macro or global terms, when the sequences of speech acts in each of the public-service advertisements in our corpus are taken together they can be construed as 'directive' speech acts. The reason for this is that the relevant public-service advertisements all underlyingly have a directive illocutionary force. The directive function, therefore, appears to quite clearly represent the major thrust or focus of the entire array of public-service advertisements. That this is the case can be further highlighted by careful examination of the illustrative public-service advertisement presented below:

Text 33

Your voting card guarantees you the right to vote. Ensure that your name is in the voter's register.

This public-service advertisement contains two speech acts. The illocutionary point in the first speech act commits the speaker to the truth of the expressed proposition: it is true that one can vote only if one has a voting card. Its direction of fit is words-to-the world: the words express what obtains. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is belief (that p): the speaker believes the expressed proposition and also wants the hearers to believe it too. We are, therefore, faced with an assertive speech act.

The illocutionary point in the second speech act exhorts Nigerians to participate in the voters' registration exercise. Its direction of fit is world-to-the words: the speaker tries to get the hearers to conform to his words. The expressed psychological state of the speech act is desire: that Nigerians participate in the voter's registration exercise. This speech act,

therefore, fulfils conditions that identify directives. It is, thus, a directive speech act.

The assertive speech act in the above **Text 33** defines the essence as well as the grounding or premise from which the directive flows. Acceptance of the one must therefore imply acceptance of the other. In macro terms, the directive is really and truly the speech act while the assertive functions essentially as an execution strategy or an expedient component of the directive. The assertive has a truth value which can only enhance the effect of the asserted proposition and consequently provide whatever motivation and/or justification is required by the directive. It is in that sense that the proposition expressed by the directive is in fact the focus of the entire advertisement.

Thus, a macro explanation of the role of the directive speech act in public-service advertisements does seem to bring the coherence of each of the public-service advertisements into relief by underscoring what can reasonably be said to hold together the individual speech acts within the discourse.

The directive speech act generally points the way to the attainment of established policy objectives. It can, thus, be argued that the basic speech act of the public-service advertisements is determined at the macro level.

This chapter has tried to concentrate on applying speech acts theory to public-service advertisements in order to identify the types of speech acts that characterize such advertisements and show the sense in which speech acts occurring in a sequence within a discourse contract some kind of relationship with one another. We have in the process shown that the directive speech act is the macro-speech act underlying public-service advertisements. Nevertheless, in order to further strengthen the claim that speech acts in a sequence do relate with one another within a discourse, the focus of the next chapter of this study will be to show that there are cohesive elements, which behaviour provides whatever confirmation is required for the claim that speech acts contract particular kinds of relationships with one another within a discourse.

CHAPTER FOUR

SPEECH ACTS IN THE PUBLIC-SERVICE ADVERTISEMENTS AND THE CONCEPT OF COHESION

Each of the public-service advertisements considered in this study is treated as a text because they each represent a unit of language in use. The point has been made elsewhere in this study (cf. 1. 2), that the public-service advertisements in our corpus were recorded from the radio. They are, therefore, spoken texts.

4.1 Text:

A text refers to any passage, spoken or written, that forms a unified whole. This is to say that a text is a unit of language in use. It is not a grammatical unit like a clause or a sentence; and it can be short or long, so it is not defined by size.

In describing a text, Halliday and Hasan (1976:2) say,

A text is best regarded as a semantic unit.

A unit not of form but of meaning. Thus it is related to a clause or sentence not by size but by REALIZATION, the coding of one symbolic system in another. A text does not consist of sentences; it is REALIZED BY, or encoded in sentences.

Thus, a text can be regarded as the basic unit of meaning in language. A distinguishing feature of a text is that it has texture.

4.2 Texture:

The concept of texture expresses the property of 'being a text'. A passage perceived as a text contains certain linguistic features which can be identified as contributing to its total unity, thereby, giving it texture. In other words, texture deals with the total unity of a text; and it is provided by the cohesive relations that exist between the items within the text. Thus, there is evidence that there exists a semantic relation within a text that defines it as a text. This semantic relation rests on the concept of cohesion.

4.3 Cohesion:

Cohesion has to do with how the text is constructed 'as a semantic edifice,' not what a text means. Halliday and Hassan (1976:4) point out that

Cohesion occurs where the INTERPRETATION of some element in the discourse is dependent on that of another. The one presupposes the other, in the sense that it cannot be effectively decoded except by recourse to it. When this happens, a relation of cohesion is set up, and the two elements, the presupposing and the presupposed, are thereby at least potentially integrated into a text.

By integration into a text, we mean that the presupposing and the presupposed items combine to create a coherent whole. In essence, the concept of cohesion is a relational one. It is the relation between one item and another that is cohesive, not the presence of a particular class of items. In this connection, consider the following public-service advertisement:

Text 12

Hoarders of essential commodities are enemies of the society.

Expose them.

The pronoun them in the second sentence refers back to (is ANAPHORIC to) Hoarders of essential commodities, in the first sentence. In other words, the word them presupposes for its interpretation something other than itself. This presupposition is met by Hoarders of essential commodities in the preceding sentence. The presupposition and its resolution provide cohesion between the two sentences. It is in this sense that the anaphoric function of them gives cohesion to the two sentences, so that we interpret them (ie, the two sentences) as a whole; and together they constitute a text. The cohesion between the two sentences is, however, brought about not just by the presence of the referring item alone but by the presence of both the referring item and the item that it refers to. It, therefore, does not suffice that there is a presupposition; the presupposition must also be resolved.

In the above public-service advertisement, the two items: them and Hoarders of essential commodities are identical in reference, or COREFERENTIAL. Coreferentiality is the cohesive agent that provides texture in this instance.

In discussing the concept of cohesion, Halliday and Hassan (1976:27-28) conclude thus:

Cohesion, therefore, is part of the text-forming component in the linguistic system. It is the means whereby elements that are structurally unrelated to one another are linked together, through the dependence of one on the other for its interpretation. The resources that make up the cohesive potential are part of the total meaning potential of the language, having a kind of catalytic function in the sense that, without cohesion, the remainder of the semantic system cannot be effectively activated at all.

This is to say that cohesion is crucial to the formation of the coherent whole termed text.

It is to be noted that the question as to whether the presupposing and or the presupposed items fall within the same sentence or not is irrelevant to the nature of the cohesive relation because cohesion is a more general notion which is above considerations of structure. Thus, cohesion occurs both within the same sentence and across sentence boundaries (ie, between sentences) because it is a general text forming relation. However, the effect of cohesion across sentence boundaries is more striking and the meaning of such cohesion is more obvious because cohesive ties between sentences are the ONLY source of texture in such contexts, whereas, within the same sentence, there are also structural relations which add to texture. Thus, in the description of a text, it is inter-sentence cohesion that is significant because it represents the variable aspect of cohesion, distinguishing one text from another.

4.4 Tie:

The term 'tie' refers to a single instance of cohesion; a term for one occurrence of a pair of cohesively related items.

Halliday and Hassan (1976:4) point out that:
The concept of a tie makes it possible to analyze a text in terms of its cohesive properties, and give a systematic account of its patterns of texture.

They identify five types of cohesive ties: reference, substitution, ellipsis, conjunction and lexical cohesion. (see Halliday and Hassan (1976) for details.)

4.5 Cohesive Ties Evident in the Public-Service

Advertisements:

The cohesive devices employed in the construction of the public-service advertisements in our data enhance the integration of the utterances into texts. Let us examine the following public-service advertisements to identify the semantic relations that exist within them.

Text 2

When we depend on government to employ everybody, then we are not being realistic. But, when we engage in self-

employment, then we are being realistic.

And, that is the sense in SAP.

In this text, the conjunction But used to start the second sentence presupposes contrast between the propositional content of the first sentence and that of the second sentence. This conjunction mediates the relationship of cohesion between the first and the second sentence. On the other hand, the demonstrative that contained in the third sentence presupposes for its interpretation something other than itself. It refers back to the second sentence. This anaphoric function of that mediates the relationship of cohesion between the second sentence and the third sentence. Thus, engaging in self-employment is the realistic thing to do and being realistic is the sense in SAP. The type of cohesive tie used in this instance is reference.

Text 14

Don't merely preach what is good
for the society.

Show it by example.

The cohesive tie used in **Text 14** is also reference. The pronoun **it** in the second sentence is anaphoric to what is good for the society in the first sentence.

Text 23

The duty to make Nigeria great belongs to us all.

Join the race to make Nigeria great.

Lexical cohesion is the cohesive tie that is in evidence in **Text 23**. It expresses itself in either the selection of the same lexical item twice, or featuring two different lexical items that are closely related semantically. **Text 23** is characterized by a repetition of 'to make Nigeria great' in the second sentence. Thus, the lexical items 'to make Nigeria great' feature in both the first and the second sentence.

Text 10

Say no to bribery and corruption. Say no to drug-abuse and trafficking. Say no to Idleness. But, yes to uprightness. Yes to

diligence. And, yes to nationalism and patriotism.

The cohesive tie evident in **Text 10** is ellipsis. Here, we observe that say is left unexpressed in the last three sentences. However, although it is unexpressed, it is still understood. The structure of these sentences presupposes some preceding item and that is the key to what has been left unexpressed. The item say in the first three sentences serves as the source of the unexpressed say. The conjunction But used to start the fourth sentence presupposes contrast between the propositions expressed by the first three sentences and that of sentences four, five and six. This conjunction mediates a relationship of cohesion between the first three sentences and the last three.

There are also instances of lexical cohesion evident in the same **Text 10**. The Text is characterized by a repetition of 'Say no to': repeated in the second and third sentences and a repetition of 'yes to': repeated in the fifth and sixth sentences. Thus, the lexical items 'Say no to' occur in the first three

sentences, while the lexical items 'yes to' occur in the last three sentences.

The preceding outline of the cohesive devices used in the public-service advertisements draws attention to the ways in which such devices enhance the integration of the sentences into texts.

4.6 Speech Acts in the Public-Service Advertisements and the Impact of Cohesion:

The bulk of the public-service advertisements in our corpus have been shown to be made up of sequences of speech acts (cf. Chapter Three). These sequences themselves have subsequently also been shown to be integrated into texts that form coherent wholes such that the speech acts relate to one another, one way or the other.

The texts, on their part, are made up of utterances. Utterances are sentences used in particular contexts; thus, they

are contextualized. It is the utterances that express the speech acts.

Like the speech act sequences, the utterances within each text relate to one another to form a coherent whole. We have tried in the immediately preceding section to show that the textual cohesion evident in the presence in the relative utterance of particular public-service advertisements is a direct result of the items that are cohesively related. The different instances of cohesion were also shown to be instances of cohesion across utterance boundaries in such a way that presupposed items and their presupposing counterparts occur in different utterances.

The analysis of the public-service advertisements with which this study is concerned within the framework provided by speech acts theory has also shown that the various speech acts contract relationships one with another within the text to achieve the desired perlocutionary intention. Thus, the concept of cohesion almost invariably, has some impact on the decod-

ing of the speech acts in the public-service advertisements because the speech acts are not only in sequences, they are also related to one another.

The impact of the concept of cohesion on the decoding of the speech acts in the public-service advertisements are such that it is only if and when the cohesively related items contained in the public-service advertisements are successfully interpreted that the appropriate speech acts can be properly understood. It is thus that successful interpretation of the directive speech act in **Text 12**, for instance,

Text 12

**Hoarders of essential commodities
are enemies of the society.**

Expose them.

requires a prior identification of the referent of the them that features in the text. It is in this sense that the concept of cohesion outlined in the preceding sections is central to not only a proper understanding and interpretation of the speech

acts in the public-service advertisements concerned, but also to the success of the perlocutionary intention associated with them, that is, getting everyone to actually conform with the appropriate exhortations.

Moreover, the presence of cohesion - engendering items in the public-service advertisements underscore the structural links between segments of particular texts and thus, play some role in highlighting and/or confirming the fact that speech acts within a discourse contract particular kinds of relations with one another. Thus, with reference to Text 12 above, the presence of the presupposing item them in the directive and the presence of the presupposed item Hoarders of essential commodities in the assertive together suggest that the directive is structurally linked to the assertive in terms that engender a relationship between them.

CHAPTER FIVE SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study set out to investigate the types of speech acts that characterize some of the public-service advertisements put out on radio in Nigeria, how these relate with one another in sequence, and the impact of cohesive elements on the speech acts.

This means in effect that this study is an attempt to apply speech acts theory to suprasentential stretches of language instead of to just isolated sentences. The public-service advertisements that constitute our corpus represent actual use of language in a real life situation rather than contrived illustrations. There is, therefore, a sense in which applying speech acts theory to extended real life discourse represents one of the contributions of this study to developments within speech acts theory. This application of speech acts theory to suprasentential stretches of language in actual usage provides evidence, if

any was required, of the relevance of speech acts to the study of real language usage because day-to-day linguistic interaction usually involves extended discourse rather than isolated sentences. Thus, we are inclined to believe that the applicability of speech acts theory to the analysis of actual discourse is the ultimate test for the viability and usefulness of the theory.

The result of the analysis of the speech acts evident in the public-service advertisements with which we have been concerned shows that Assertives and Directives are the predominant types of speech acts used in the advertisements. There are no instances of Commissives, Expressives and Declarations in any of the advertisements, thus suggesting that these speech act types may not be effective in achieving the goals of a mass mobilization programme. The result reveals that 57.0% of the speech acts in the public-service advertisements are Assertives while 43.0% are Directives and that the assertives generally provide motivation for the directives whenever they occur within the same speech act sequence.

The present study of public-service advertisements makes clear the sense in which speech acts do not normally occur in isolation in real life, rather they come in sequences within a discourse. The analysis also shows that in sequences within a discourse, speech acts tend to contract special relationships with one another. Three types of relationships which such speech acts so contract were identified, namely, relations of justification, amplification, and contrastive apposition. The configuration of speech act types was shown to be such that assertive speech acts and directive speech acts co-occur in sequences mediated by a relation of justification, while only identical speech act types co-occur in sequences marked by either a relation of amplification or that of contrastive apposition. The macro-speech act of the public-service advertisements was shown to be the directive speech act.

The analysis, however, raises an important issue which deserves further study: the issue of interpreting relations between multiple instances of speech acts sequences contained in one text where such speech act clusters have the same

goal (cf. Chapter three: Texts 4 & 10). The question is whether in assigning relationship types to such speech act sequences, we should regard speech acts that share the same goal as single speech acts and, thus, treat them as independent entities or whether we should, as we have in the present study, simply regard them as speech act clusters which have the same goal and can therefore be treated as one group. The resolution of the issues involved in the question raised here will have to await future research on the subject.

In analysing the impact on the speech acts of the cohesive elements evident in the public-service advertisements, the place and role of cohesion in the decoding of speech acts is shown to be such that it is only if and when such cohesion-engendering items are successfully interpreted that the relevant speech acts can be properly understood. The study also draws attention to the sense in which the presence of cohesion-engendering related items in public-service advertisements provides further justification for the fact that in discourse speech acts do relate with one another. The recognition of the

impact of cohesive elements on the speech acts in our public-service advertisements and the recognition of the fact that such elements play some role in highlighting and confirming the claim that within a discourse speech acts do relate with one another, represent some of the contributions of this study to underscoring the effect of textual features on speech acts theory.

In addition, the application of speech acts theory to public-service advertisements provides some insight into the linguistic nature of public-service advertising. Thus, the analysis has drawn attention to the types of speech acts and speech act relationships that characterize public-service advertising. The findings of this study should, therefore, properly increase the linguistic awareness of copywriters and thus help them create even better and more effective public-service and other analogous advertisements.

It is against the backdrop provided by all of the above that we are inclined to argue that the application of speech acts

theory to various instances of discourse, such as court sessions, doctor-patient interactions, board meeting sessions and such other social interactions may well yield further insights into the nature and/or whatever hitherto unknown factors or phenomena impact on such instances of language use in real life. These, therefore, represent possible directions of future research into the relative value and/or continued relevance of speech acts theory as a viable tool for the investigation of extended discourse.

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APPENDIXES

Appendix A: Collection of the public-service advertisements used for this study:

A. SAP-related Public-Service Advertisements:

Text 1

Farming has always been a noble profession in our land. It will even be worthier to farm in these days of self-reliance. Let us go back to the land and make Nigeria grow.

Text 2

When we depend on government to employ everybody, then we are not being realistic. But, when we engage in self-

employment, then we are being realistic.
And, that is the sense in SAP.

Text 3

True, times are hard. True, cost of living is high, and you are feeling the pain and the strain. But your sacrifice is what is right. Remember, after rain comes shine.

Text 4

Hard times are here but not forever. Everyone has got a dream. You've got yours and I've got mine. What it takes is guts and sacrifice to pull this country through or your dreams will fade away. Yea, what it takes is guts and sacrifice to pull this country through. Hard times are like bad dreams, but they don't last forever. Don't despair.

Text 5

Come. Let's reason together. There is a saying that old habits die hard. But, if a man comes face to face with some stark realities of life, he will have to adjust. It's time to change our style. It's time to look inwards. When was the last time you bought a pair of shoes? Was it imported? Not likely, because it does not make sense spending a thousand naira for imported shoes when for ten times less you can have long-lasting made in Nigeria shoes. Same goes for other items. It's time to make Nigeria truly a nation. Take the food sector, Nigeria possesses one of the highest varieties of food in the world.

We have maize, rice, beans, yam, millet, plus all the fish and meat needed for a balanced meal. Why must we suffer in the

midst of plenty? It's time to make Nigeria truly a Nation. National self-reliance or foreign economic slavery, the choice is yours.

Text 6

Had taim no bi kọs o! I de hapun to ẹvribodi from taim to taim. If yu tink se had taim na kọs, yu mis rod bad bad. And if yu tink se na yu di tin bad fọ pas, wet ọntil yu hiẹ di ọda man tori, yu go tank Ọd. Bọt kọm o! Wi sabi hala o! I de hapun fọ ẹvri kọntri o! Ehen, no bi onli Naigeria i de.

Fọ sọm pipul, kọntri had be se dem no fit bai big moto, chọp fat fat lọch, ọl dem maut go de mek miẹ miẹ. Dem no fit travl go ẹniwiẹ az dem laik, go chọp laif. Bọt luk yọ brọda, ples fọ slip na wahala,

kõmon to sok gari tek salut belle fõ monin,
 nmm, hu dash monki? Sek of se som pipul
 mos to mek big profit. Ai tek God beg yu,
 tek am izi. Az kontrin tanda so, mek awa
 hed no jomp komot in bodi o! Had taim no
 bi kos o! I de hapun to eviribodi from taim
 to taim. Dis taim, na im bukuru pipul de
 kol fez. I go kom, den i go go.

**B. MAMSER-related Public-Service
 Advertisements:**

Text 7

Be committed to your job. A full day's
 pay demands a full day's work.

Text 8

One of the social ills in our midst is
 favouritism. Reward people on merit and
 not on other considerations.

Text 9

Be a good Nigerian. Buy home-made goods.

Text 10

Say no to bribery and corruption. Say no to drug-abuse and trafficking. Say no to idleness. But, yes to uprightness. Yes to diligence. And, yes to nationalism and patriotism.

Text 11

Think of what you will do for your country and not what your country will do for you.

Text 12

Hoarders of essential commodities are enemies of the society. Expose them.

Text 13

First come, first served. Don't be in a hurry. Please, join the queue.

Text 14

Don't merely preach what is good for the society. Show it by example.

Text 15

Nigerian youth, let's take the part to tolerance and unity. And, when we grow up we can hold the nation together.

Text 16

You have a job in your life. Put life into your job.

Text 17

Remember your pledge to the nation.
Serve Nigeria with all your strength.

Text 18

As you step out today, put your nation first.

Text 19

Mi ai laik mai kɔntri. Ai laik di land and pipul. Eviri tin i de fɔ Nigeria. Mek we join hand, to mek Naigeria greta. Ai laik am. Ai laik am o!.

C. Political Education Public-Service Advertisements:

Text 20

Think of what you will do for your country. Support the transition programme.

Text 21

Be part of the move towards democracy. Support the transition programme.

Text 22

Be patriotic. Support the government's transition to civil rule programme.

Text 23

The duty to make Nigeria great belongs to us all. Join the race to make Nigeria great.

Text 24

In the nineties and beyond, let us resolve to make Nigeria a better place.

Text 25

The transition period calls for patriotism. Be patriotic.

Text 26

The third republic is around the corner. The two political parties, SDP and NRC, belong to us all. No founder. No follower.

Text 27

Social Democratic Party (SDP), National Republican Convention (NRC) di tu pati we govrment apruv na wi on. Baba ke no de fo dis won at ol. E viribodi na ikuol memba o!.

Text 28

NRC and SDP are the parties recognized by government. Enlighten yourself on the two of these parties. Get copies of their manifestoes today.

Text 29

The third republic will decide the future of the country. Let honesty be your watchword as you get ready for 1990.

Text 30

Be committed to the return of democracy. Don't hinder the implementation of the transition programme.

Text 31

To ensure a hitch-free election, it is important that you identify your party colour. The colour of Social Democratic Party (SDP) is green. On the other hand, the colour of National Republican Convention (NRC) is white. Knowing your party is knowing the colour of identification.

Text 32

Nigeria is one. Forget tribalism and be tolerant. Let us all join hands to lead Nigeria to greatness in the third republic.

Text 33

Your voting card guarantees you the right to vote. Ensure that your name is in the voter's register.

Text 34

A good and responsible government does not come by chance. Vote sensibly to ensure this.

Text 35

It is a grave mistake to be involved in electoral offences. Refrain from them.

Text 36

Your duty to the fatherland is to help keep the peace at election time. Join security forces to achieve this objective.

Text 37

It is your civic responsibility to maintain law and order during election time. Let us all maintain the peace.

Text 38

Play politics with spirit of sportsmanship. Accept the verdict of the people calmly.

Text 39

Ensure the success of democracy. Vote for honest leaders.

Text 40

You have nothing to lose but everything to gain by voting massively on the election day. Make sure you exercise this right as a good citizen.

Text 41

Do not sell your votes. They form part of your weapon to install a good government in the country.

Text 42

Don't throw away your votes. Elect leaders that you can trust and are patriotic.

Text 43

Ensure that you cast your vote on the election day. It is your right and civic responsibility.

Text 44

Violence and other malpractices are prohibited by law during election. Punishments for offenders are very heavy indeed.

Text 45

Political thuggery, violence in politics, bribery and corruption, impersonation, undue influence, canvassing for votes or carrying dangerous weapons on election days - Oyo State NEC say 'No'.

Text 46

Nothing will change if you sit and fold your arms. It's your chance. Get up, get up, come and vote. Your vote is your power. Use it wisely. Nigerians, this is your golden opportunity to choose people of proven integrity, worthy candidates to represent you. Yes, every adult over eighteen years must vote to help shape the destiny of our nation. Don't sell your vote. It's your power. Use it.

Text 47

Sidon de luk, notin go hapun o!
 Beta no go kom if yu no trai o!
 Bot if yu vot, yu go chuz di best tin fo
 helep yo laif o mek i beta. Go vot no bi
 kos. Dat pepa we yu kari, no bi kwe kwe
 pepa o, na pawa! Yo vot na yo pawa. No
 tro we am o! Pesin we de krai o de si rodu
 o! Notin fit chengi if yu jost tanda gbite
 wit strong fes laik se laif don mona yu. Na
 yo hand dis won de o! Yu don get pawa
 naw. Dat vot we yu kari na heleba pawa.
 Tek am put beta pesin we yu sho se i get
 beta karacta, mek i helep mek Naigeria
 beta. Eviribodi, wons yu don pas etin
 yies, yu fit vot. Na yo taim bi dis. If yu let
 am fele, wota don pas gari bi dat. Mai
 friend, no sel yo vot o! Na yo pawa bi dat.
 Yuz am!

Yọ vot na yọ pawa. No tro we am o! Pẹsin
we de krai o de si rodu o!

Text 48

Political ambition is a legitimate aspiration. Do not corrupt the society to realize your dream. Nigeria deserves excellent leadership.

Text 49

Political leaders should always think and programme well for the masses who vote them in. Public office means public trust.

Text 50

Ai wọn bi ọga, i izi fọ tok. If yu wọn be
bẹta ọga, opun yọ iẹ, hiẹ yọ pipul o! Na
dẹm put yu dẹ o!

Appendix B: Charts showing contextual background of the public-service advertisements and types and numbers of speech acts found in them:

Contextual Background	Texts	<u>Types and Numbers of Speech Acts</u>				
		Asser- tives	Direc- tives	Commis- sives	Expres- sives	Declara- tions
SAP-related	1	2	2	-	-	-
Public-service	2	3	-	-	-	-
Advertisements	3	4	1	-	-	-
	4	10	1	-	-	-
	5	11	5	-	-	-
	6	16	6	-	-	-
MAMSER-related	7	1	1	-	-	-
Public-service	8	1	2	-	-	-
Advertisements	9	-	2	-	-	-
	10	-	6	-	-	-
	11	-	2	-	-	-
	12	1	1	-	-	-
	13	2	2	-	-	-
	14	-	2	-	-	-
	15	1	1	-	-	-
	16	1	1	-	-	-
	17	-	2	-	-	-
	18	-	1	-	-	-
	19	5	1	-	-	-
Political Education	20	-	2	-	-	-
Public-sevice	21	-	2	-	-	-
Advertisements	22	-	2	-	-	-

Contextual Background	Texts	<u>Types and Numbers of Speech Acts</u>				
		Asser- tives	Dirrec- tives	Commis- sives	Expres- sives	Declara- tions
	23	1	1	-	-	-
	24	-	1	-	-	-
	25	1	1	-	-	-
	26	4	-	-	-	-
	27	3	-	-	-	-
	28	1	2	-	-	-
	29	1	1	-	-	-
	30	-	2	-	-	-
	31	4	-	-	-	-
	32	1	3	-	-	-
	33	1	1	-	-	-
	34	1	1	-	-	-
	35	1	1	-	-	-
	36	1	1	-	-	-
	37	1	1	-	-	-
	38	-	2	-	-	-
	39	-	2	-	-	-
	40	2	1	-	-	-
	41	1	1	-	-	-
	42	-	2	-	-	-
	43	1	1	-	-	-
	44	2	-	-	-	-
	45	1	-	-	-	-
	46	6	7	-	-	-
	47	18	5	-	-	-
	48	2	1	-	-	-
	49	1	1	-	-	-
	50	2	1	-	-	-

Appendix C: Percentage total of each category of speech acts found in the data:

(i) Contextual Background	Total Number of Speech Acts	Total Number of Speech Act Types		Total % per Speech Act Type	
		Asser	Direc	Asser	Direc
		tives	tives	tives	tives
SAP-related Public-Service Advertisements	61	46	15	75.4%	24.6%
MAMSER-related Public-Service Advertisements	36	12	24	33.3%	66.7%
Political Education Public-Service Advertisements	103	56	47	54.4%	45.6%
(ii) Speech Act Type	Total Number	Total %			
Assertives	114	57.0%			
Directives	86	43.0%			

(iii) Number of Public-Service Advertisements Analyzed		Total Number of Speech Acts
SAP-related:	6	61
MAMSER-related:	13	36
Political Education-related:	31	103
Total:	50	200

Appendix D: Chart showing contextual background of the Public-Service Advertisements and types of relationships found in them:

Contextual Background	Text	Types of Relationship
SAP-related Public-Service Advertisements	1	Justification / Amplification
	2	Contrastive Apposition
	3	Justification
	4	Contrastive Apposition / Justification
	5	Justification
	6	Justification
MAMSER-related Public-Service Advertisements	7	Justification
	8	Justification / Contrastive Apposition
Advertisements	9	Amplification
	10	Contrastive Apposition
	11	Contrastive Apposition

	12	Justification
	13	Justification
	14	Contrastive Apposition
	15	Justification
	16	Justification
	17	Amplification
	18	Single Unit in Isolation
	19	Justification
Political Education	20	Amplification
Public-Service	21	Amplification
Advertisements	22	Amplification
	23	Justification
	24	Single Unit in Isolation
	25	Justification
	26	Amplification / Contrastive Apposition
	27	Amplification
	28	Justification / Amplification
	29	Justification
	30	Amplification
	31	Amplification / Contrastive Apposition
	32	Justification / Contrastive Apposition / Amplification
	33	Justification
	34	Justification
	35	Justification

36	Justification
37	Justification
38	Amplification
39	Amplification
40	Contrastive Apposition / Justification
41	Justification
42	Contrastive Apposition
43	Justification
44	Amplification
45	Single Unit in Isolation
46	Justification
47	Justification
48	Justification
49	Justification
50	Justification

Appendix E: Percentage total of each type of relationship found in the data:

(i) Contextual Background	Total Number of Relationship Types.			
	Justifi- cation	Amplifi- cation	Contrastive Apposition	Single Unit
SAP-related Public- Service Advertisements	5	1	2	-
MAMSER-related Public- Service Advertisements	7	2	4	1
Political Education Public- Service Advertisements	18	12	5	2

(ii) Relationship Type	Total Number	Total %
Justification	30	50.9%
Amplification	15	25.4%
Contrastive Apposition	11	18.6%
Single Unit in Isolation	3	5.1%